

GUIDANCE REPORT FOR POTENTIAL ROLE OF CARBON OFFSETTING SCHEMES AND PARIS AGREEMENT

A DISCUSSION PAPER ON THE VALORISATION OF EMISSION REDUCTIONS,
CARBON REMOVALS, AND ON THE COMPLEMENTARITY OF CLIMATE
INCENTIVE SCHEMES

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Land-use based Mitigation for Resilient Climate Pathways

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Short Summary of results

This report assesses several relevant climate incentive schemes within the European policy context, where we discuss the differing and overlapping features of the GHG monitoring, reporting and verification systems associated with the individual schemes. We argue that there is an increasing need to provide the EU markets for reduction and removal actions with better governance and clarity on the best ways to (financially) valorise the (claimed) climate performances. We argue that a pro-active governance strategy - that safeguards the 'complementarity' of the different relevant climate incentive schemes - is required to aid and guide the markets in their efforts to contribute to mitigating climate change.

Evidence of accomplishment

This report

About LANDMARC

Negative emission solutions are expected to play a pivotal role in future climate actions and net zero emissions policy scenarios. To date most climate actions have focussed on phasing out fossil fuels and reducing greenhouse gas emissions in, for example, industry, electricity, and transport. While zero emission trajectories in these sectors will remain a priority for decades to come, it is expected that residual GHG emissions will remain. To be able to fulfil the Paris Agreement and meet the world's climate goals research, policy and markets are increasingly looking at negative emission solutions.

This is why the nineteen LANDMARC consortium partners work together in order to:

- Estimate the climate impact of land-based negative emission solutions, in agriculture, forestry, and other land-use sectors
- Assess the potential for regional and global upscaling of negative emission solutions
- Map their potential environmental, economic, and social co-benefits and trade-offs

LANDMARC is an interdisciplinary consortium with expertise from ecology, engineering, climate sciences, global carbon cycle, soil sciences, satellite earth observation sciences, agronomy, economics, social sciences, and business. There is a balanced representation of partners from academia, SMEs, and NGOs from the EU, Africa, Asia and the Americas, which ensures a wide coverage of LMTs operating in different contexts (e.g. climates, land-use practices, socio-economic etc.) and spatial scales.

The LANDMARC project consortium:

Preface

During the development of this report the authors set out to produce a D2.5 ‘Guidance report for potential role of carbon offsetting schemes and Paris Agreement’. After a number of (online) stakeholder sessions and interviews on the challenges of (financial) valorisation of land-based reduction and removal practices, often labelled as negative emissions technologies and practices (NETPs), carbon dioxide removal solutions (CDRs) or land-based mitigation technologies (LMTs), Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and/or carbon farming, it became apparent that there is a great demand for knowledge transfer and capacity building in the area of (voluntary) carbon markets.

Although carbon markets are already in existence for a long-time, there are still many world regions, countries, local communities, farmer cooperatives, etc. that do not yet have the knowledge, capacity and/or resources to access carbon markets. However, at the same time the authors acknowledge that there already is a large body of scientific, market and policy literature available that provides good quality insights on (voluntary) carbon markets. Many lessons on baselines, permanence, additionality and other specific carbon market rules and provisions have been further discussed and developed since the flexible mechanisms CDM and JI of the Kyoto Protocol; see for example (Foundation Future of the Carbon Market, 2021). Also, there are ample reports and online webinar materials and market information available¹ that provide insights into the functioning of carbon markets and/or an broader overview and outlook on the state and trends within carbon markets and/or carbon pricing mechanisms, such as (The World Bank, 2022) and (Ecosystem Marketplace, 2021).

In order not to repeat or synthesise many of the arguments used in the ongoing debate about the (future) role of (voluntary) carbon markets, the authors decided to assess the role of the voluntary carbon market in conjunction with a range of existing or new climate incentive schemes. While voluntary carbon markets provide a promising incentive for many reduction and removal actions, there are also a broad range of other climate incentives that either compete with or can complement carbon markets. This report assesses several relevant climate incentive schemes within the European policy context, where we discuss the differing and overlapping features of the GHG monitoring, reporting and verification systems associated with the individual schemes. We argue that there is an increasing need to provide the EU markets for reduction and removal actions with better governance and clarity on the best ways to (financially) valorise the (claimed) climate performances. We argue that a proactive governance strategy - that safeguards the ‘complementarity’ of the different relevant climate incentive schemes - is required to aid and guide the markets in their efforts to contribute to mitigating climate change.

¹ See for example:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ycZiYtvzsIA>

<https://www.climatefocus.com/initiatives/voluntary-carbon-market-dashboard>

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Abbreviations

- AD** – Anaerobic Digestion
- AFOLU** – Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use
- BKE** – ‘Broeikasgaseenheden’ (Greenhouse gas units)
- CAP** – Common Agricultural Policy
- CBAM** – Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
- CCR** – Carbon Capture and Reuse
- CCS** – Carbon Capture and Storage
- CCU** – Carbon Capture and Utilization
- CH₄** - Methane
- CO₂** – carbon dioxide
- COP** – Conference of the Parties
- DACCS** – Direct Air CO₂ Capture and Storage
- EC** – European Commission
- EEX** – European Energy Exchange
- EF** – Emission Factor
- EU ETS** – European Union Emissions Trading System
- EUA** – European Union emission allowances
- GHG** – Greenhouse gases
- GoO** – Guarantees of Origin
- GWP** – Global Warming Potential
- HBE / REU** – ‘Hernieuwbare Brandstofeenheden’ (Renewable Fuel Units; RFU)
- ILUC** – Indirect Land Use Change
- IPCC** – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- ISCC** – International Sustainability and Carbon Certification
- ITMOs** – Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes
- KPIs** – Key Performance Indicators
- LCA** – Life Cycle Assessment
- LMT** – Land-based mitigation technologies and practices
- LULUCF** – Land Use, Land Use Change, Forestry
- MRV** – Monitoring, Reporting and Verification
- N₂O** – Nitrous oxide
- NCM** – Netherlands Centre for Manure Valorisation
- NEa** – Netherlands Emissions Authority
- NIR** – National Greenhouse Gas emissions Inventory Report
- OMGE** - overall mitigation in global emissions
- RDF** – Refuse derived fuels
- RED** – Renewable Energy Directive
- SDE** – ‘Stimulerend Duurzame Energieproductie en Klimaattransitie’
- SNK** – Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt (Dutch voluntary carbon market foundation)
- TOF** – Trees outside Forest
- UNFCCC** – United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change

Summary

The European Commission intends to regulate the certification of carbon removals (DG CLIMA, 2022). The purpose of this regulatory framework is to stimulate innovative techniques and methods aimed at the capture, storage, and reuse of CO₂/carbon, as well as emission reductions. A robust certification system is an important precondition for the eventual (financial) valorisation of climate performances that can be delivered by farmers, forest managers and companies/industries in the bio-based and circular economy.

There is a wide range of projects and activities that can contribute to the reduction and removal of carbon in soils, forests, materials, chemicals, etc. This includes nature-based solutions such as peatland/wetland restoration, permanent grassland, and forest planting, among others. This is often referred to as *carbon farming* because they are directly linked to some form of land use. In addition, there are also various projects focussing on the (re)use of biogenic/fossil carbon or biobased raw materials in the bio-based and circular economy. This includes the application of biochar or organic fertilisers (soil carbon accumulation), as well as carbon removal in building and construction materials or other products (e.g., furniture, crates, plastics, chemicals). There is also a category with more technical or engineered measures, such as direct air capture CCS, blue hydrogen, where the captured (fossil) CO₂ is stored underground (CCS) or reused (CCU).

Irrespective of the much-needed certification of the climate performances in the above-mentioned activities, there will be an increasing drive to (financially) valorise these climate services via different climate policies and incentive schemes. A viable business model needs to be established, for example, carbon farming. Under current market conditions, most of the above-mentioned activities, will require some considerable amount of financial support. This support can come via a range of policy schemes, but also other (voluntary) incentive schemes, like the (voluntary) carbon market. Quite a few of the existing policies and incentive schemes already provide partial or some level of financial support for carbon reduction or removal actions. In this report we will argue that there will be an increasing need to ensure that the individual climate incentive schemes (i.e., schemes that reward reduction or removal performances) and their associated GHG accounting systems are properly aligned.

Safeguarding the coherence or '**complementarity**' of the climate incentive schemes will be necessary to not only prevent over market stimulation, double counting and/or fraud, but also to provide the much-needed transparency and clarity to market actors in their search for the needed financial and social return for the climate service delivered.

The relevant mix of incentives includes both the EU Emissions Trading scheme and non-ETS incentive schemes. We elaborate on this policy mix in more detail, using the Dutch context as an example. Most incentive schemes are aligned with the relevant EU directives and policy frameworks (e.g., Common Agricultural Policy, EU ETS Directive, Renewable Energy Directive) thus lessons can be potentially applied to other Member States. Looking at a relevant mix of incentives for carbon farming activities in the Netherlands, we have:

- The *European Emission Trading System (EU ETS)*: this system represents about half of the European economy's CO₂ emissions and puts a price on emitting CO₂. It mainly targets the industry and energy sectors,

In addition to the EU ETS, there are several non-ETS incentive schemes in The Netherlands that focus on other sectors, including:

- The *Renewable Energy for Transport (HBE) scheme*: focuses primarily on the transport sector whereby the blended renewable fuels must meet a certain minimum greenhouse gas emission reduction performance threshold;
- The *subsidy scheme for sustainable energy production and climate transition (SDE++)*: focuses on various project categories that contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and the storage of CO₂,
- The *eco-scheme*: is a new instrument within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), whereby CAP payments are awarded to so-called eco-activities in the agricultural sector. This instrument will work with a scoring system, whereby points will also be awarded for climate services; and
- The *voluntary national carbon market (SNK)*: focuses on climate projects and initiatives that can apply for carbon certificates via the 'Stichting Nationale Koolstofmarkt' (SNK) or Foundation National Carbon market, considering that the climate services delivered are additional to the government's current climate policies (policy additionality).

All five climate schemes provide a financial incentive for one or more carbon farming (or closely related) activities. Although each incentive scheme has its own or multiple specific goal(s), they all have the climate goal as a common denominator (see Table 1). In addition, each scheme has its own list of eligible activities (see Table 3 in Section 1.2).

Table 1: Policy goals per climate incentive scheme

	Climate	Renewable energy	Soil & air	Biodiversity	Landscape	Water
EU ETS	X					
HBE	X	X				
SDE++	X	X				
Eco-scheme	X		X	X	X	X
SNK	X					

Based upon an initial assessment, we found that in several cases there can be a significant potential overlap, where the same or similar activities may be eligible for more than one incentive scheme. Therefore, it is not always clear:

- for which activity,
- for what climate (or other eco-system) service, and
- under which incentive scheme,

one can apply or obtain funding. Funding can be considered via a direct subsidy (SDE), renewable energy unit (HBE), emission allowance (EUA), eco-scheme premium (CAP) and/or carbon certificate (SNK).

In addition to the envisaged European certification framework, which will be based on state-of-the-art GHG Monitoring (M) and certification of climate services, each of the five policy instruments require a GHG accounting system for Reporting and Verification (RV) of the climate service delivered (or climate performance claimed).

GHG accounting is needed to justify the (financial) support under the respective scheme. All five schemes have a certain GHG accounting system of varying complexity, each with its own rules (e.g., pools, activities, and gases to be included, baselines and accounting rules). To illustrate the basic differences in the GHG accounting systems for the five schemes we use the framing of the Scope 1, 2 and 3 approach from the GHG Protocol (WRI, 2013).

Scope 1, 2, 3 approach

Scope 1 corresponds to the emissions that are owned or under direct control of the organisation.

Scope 2 takes into account the emissions from purchased electricity, heat, cooling, etc.

Scope 3 takes into account the greenhouse gas emissions from both purchased products and the use of produced products by customers and waste processing.

An initial (limited) assessment of the five selected incentive schemes shows clear similarities and differences with respect to the scope of GHG accounting system. In Figure 1 we illustrate the sub scope(s) of the five schemes' underlying GHG accounting systems. We distinguish between the following five (sub)scope(s):

- Scope 1: Direct effects: emissions related to the company/activity
- Scope 2: Indirect effects: energy-related emissions outside own organisation
 - Sub-scope 2.1: Domestic
 - Sub-scope 2.2: Abroad
- Scope 3: Indirect effects: other indirect chain-related effects outside own organisation
 - Sub-scope 3.1: Domestic
 - Sub-scope 3.2: Abroad

We have split up scope 2 and 3 climate impacts into a domestic and foreign impact, as several GHG accounting schemes have chosen to exclude foreign or target only domestic climate effects.

We then qualitatively assessed the extent to which all five sub scopes are covered by each incentive scheme (0 = all GHG impacts of sub scope fully excluded and 5 = all GHG impacts of sub scope fully included; see Table 2 for further explanations).

The GHG accounting system associated with the eco-scheme and the EU ETS are primarily scope 1 systems. Other effects scope 2, 3 effects up- or downstream in the value chain are in principle not included in the accounting. However, in the case of the EU ETS, there is an option to the capture, transfer, and underground storage of CO₂. For the other schemes (SNK, HBE and SDE++), specific rules and provisions apply for whether scope 2 and 3 (domestic and foreign) climate effects must be included.

Figure 1: Scope of GHG accounting systems of five incentive schemes (based on limited analysis)

Figure 1 provides an indicative and oversimplified visualisation of the information in Table 2 (below), where we describe in more detail which scope(s) apply and which calculation rules and/or exceptions apply (see Section 1.3).

Table 2: Scope and basic GHG accounting rules per incentive scheme (initial assessment)

Incentive	Climate impact	Scope 1 (direct)	Scope 2 (indirect energy) & 3 (in-direct chain related)	
			Domestic	Foreign
EU ETS	Emissions	Yes, within installation boundary	No	No, but perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification
	Reductions	-	Yes, via avoided fossil CO ₂ and CCS of fossil CO ₂	No, but perhaps indirectly via the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
	Removals	No	No, captured biogenic CO ₂ does not receive additional incentive under EU ETS-CCS regime	No, but perhaps indirectly via the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
HBE	Emissions	Yes	Yes, via use energy during cultivation, harvest, transport, processing, and carbon stock changes associated with the biomass feedstock and perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification	
	Reductions	-	Yes, avoided fossil fuel, and via CCS and CCR (carbon capture recycling) of fossil CO ₂	
	Removals	-	Yes, via carbon storage in soils and via CCS and CCR of biogenic CO ₂	

Incentive	Climate impact	Scope 1 (direct)	Scope 2 (indirect energy) & 3 (in-direct chain related)	
			Domestic	Foreign
SDE++	Emissions	Yes	Yes, via energy usage	No, but perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification
	Reductions	-	Partial, via avoided fossil CO ₂ and avoided methane	No
	Removals	Yes, via CCS as separate eligible activity	No	No
Eco-scheme	Emissions	Yes	No	No
	Reductions	Yes (?), on own parcel/land	No	No
	Removals	Yes (?), on own parcel/land	No	No
SNK	Emissions	Yes	Yes	No (?)
	Reductions	-	Yes	Yes, via specific rule within the SNK Rulebook (SNK, 2021)
	Removals	-	Yes	

Because of the following 4 key issues listed below, there will be a great need to safeguard the coherence, or rather the **complementarity**, of the current and future climate incentives framework.

1. The lists of eligible (climate) activities for the different climate schemes shows significant potential overlap (see Section 1.2 and Table 3),
2. The existing GHG accounting systems for each incentive scheme differ in terms of:
 - a. Scope 1, 2 and 3 coverage (Section 0)
 - b. Allocation of emissions, reductions and removals to individual activities, companies, or end products (Section 0)
 - c. Use of default (calculation) values or minimum performance thresholds (Section 0)
3. Not all GHG accounting use the same rules and provisions for:
 - a. Certification of the sustainability of land use and biomass (Section 0)
 - b. Transfer (implicit) of GHG emissions, reductions, or removals (Section 0)
 - c. Non-permanence of carbon removal (Section 0)
4. There is a continuously changing framework of incentives and policies (Section 1.4), e.g.
 - a. EU ETS extension to the built environment and transport
 - b. New scoring system for eco-activities under the eco-scheme regulations of CAP
 - c. The HBE scheme (energy units) is set to become the BKE system (GHG units)

This will provide the market with the transparency and clarity it needs in its search for the right (financial) return for the climate services they intend to deliver (in real practice, the valorisation of climate services is often still a time-consuming search).

We anticipate that there will be many activities / projects (cases) for activities within the carbon farming domain, where the financial compensation for the climate service delivered will be based on a combination of funding from different incentive schemes. It is often still not clear which combinations of financial incentives are allowed or on which grounds certain combinations are

rejected. There are only limited and often not uniform provisions for assessing the additionality and complementarity of mixes of incentives schemes.

The national governments of the EU Member States, as well as the EU has a pivotal governance role to provide proper rules and guidance to the markets. Adequate governance of the complementarity of climate incentive schemes, for example within The Netherlands, would require the involvement of different ministries (linked to the relevant incentive schemes), but also a broad range of market actors from agriculture, forestry, (bio-based, circular) industry, energy, and transport sectors. The private sector from the carbon farming, bio-based industry and circular economy domain can also contribute to this effort by providing empirical evidence of cases / projects where the valorisation of the climate service/claim is not clear given the relevant spectrum of climate incentive schemes.

Introduction

1.1 Taxonomy discussion of reductions and removals

The European Commission (EC) is planning to regulate the certification of so-called 'carbon removals' (DG CLIMA, 2022). A robust certification system is an important precondition for the (financial) valorisation of climate performances that can be delivered by for example farmers, forest managers and companies/industries in the bio-based and circular economy. This will stimulate innovative techniques and methods aimed at the capture, storage, and reuse of CO₂/carbon.

The LANDMARC project defines so-called Land-based Mitigation Technologies and practices (LMTs). These are negative emissions technologies that remove and sequester carbon dioxide through land management. We also emphasize “practice”, that is, the human interventions needed to reduce emissions and to implement and promote carbon sequestration. In broader terms, LMTs can be divided into three groups. Agriculture, forestry, and other land use sectors are potentially able to absorb huge amounts of carbon from the atmosphere. They form natural processes and there are many potential co-benefits of improving land management, such as forest restoration. However, biomass, and oil carbon pools are not permanent and slowly built-up carbon stocks can be released rapidly after management changes or land conversion, e.g., through deforestation. Moreover, LMTs compete for land as a scarce resource. Therefore, mitigation technologies involving land management need to be well-integrated to avoid trade-offs, e.g., risks for food security.

Thus, there is a wide range of land-based activities and measures that can make a positive climate contribution. In the absence of a uniform European and scientific taxonomy in this area, we provide a brief discussion on relevant concepts, activities, and measures.

For this report, we consider land-based negative emission solutions (removal), as well as a range of linked land-based actions that also can contribute to reducing emissions (reduction). We find that both reduction and removal impacts of often part of the same value chain and thus should be considered simultaneously within any governance regime.

Although the EC focuses (EC, 2021) explicitly on the certification of carbon removals (the extraction and sequestration of CO₂ from the atmosphere; so-called negative emissions), it is to be expected that in the development of a carbon removal certification regime, also greenhouse gas emissions (fluxes) and emission reductions in agriculture and biomass processing sectors will also be taken into account. We observe that in practice, emissions, reductions, and removals are often strongly connected within one project or organisation. Figure 2 (below) distinguishes between i) **nature-based**, ii) **biomass-based** and iii) **engineered** reduction and removal measures.

Nature-based measures include activities in agriculture and forestry, where based on (accelerating or preventing) natural processes, such as photosynthesis, mineralisation, oxidation, weathering, desiccation, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from soils and vegetation take place avoiding the

depletion or supporting the increase of carbon stocks. Examples of this are e.g., no-tillage, peatland rewetting and tree planting. Many measures in this category also fall under the heading of 'carbon farming'.

In terms of carbon removals these options generally have a low level of permanence when compared to other biomass-based and engineered removal options. For many *carbon farming* options the bulk of the buffered carbon remains in the active 'short' carbon cycle (i.e. it can be re-released into the atmosphere due to natural processes, by climate events or by human actions), while at the same time there is ample evidence to suggest that carbon farming actions provide a potentially wide variety of other environmental and socio-economic co-benefits (e.g. regenerative agriculture, ecosystem services, biodiversity, air quality, rural development).

In the following we refer to LMTs as a concept to group activities and measures aiming at land-based carbon removals and emission reductions.

The ***biomass-based category*** encompasses a wide range of activities that are part of the bio-based and/or circular economy. This usually involves the processing of (recycled) biomass as a raw material² in a certain way and using them in an end product, such as energy and building materials. When these products replace conventional products produced with fossil raw materials, they result in emission reductions. There may also be (temporary) carbon storage in an intermediate or final bio-based product. Examples of this include biochar, wood as construction material, new bio-based insulation materials and bio-chemicals, but also organic fertilisers, bioenergy carbon capture and storage, etc.

Depending on the specific end-use of the biogenic carbon stored, this category typically has a potentially higher level of storage permanence. This is because the bio-based value chains and associated processes are taking place in a more 'controlled' environment (i.e., mass balance, material flow). In terms of associated co-benefits, this category - which relies on the cultivation, management and extraction of large quantities of biomass resources from the natural environment - tends to raise more concerns on the sustainable use of biomass (i.e. trade-offs) relative to many nature-based options.

The key distinction with options in the biomass-based category relates to the notion that these value chains rely mainly on the processing of fossil carbon or cause fossil CO₂ emissions. As such, these options only contribute as a reduction option, and not contribute to the net removal of carbon from the atmosphere.

² Including the organic fraction of wastes.

Figure 2: Overview of ‘nature-based’, ‘biomass-based’ and ‘engineered’ reduction and removal activities on land and oceans (non-exhaustive overview)

Source: Own illustrations, LANDMARC (2022)

The '**engineered**' category includes various measures that do not (primarily) rely on natural processes and/or processing of bio-based raw materials. These measures have a strong technological component whereby often fossil-based resources are processed, and/or fossil CO₂ is captured, stored underground (CCS) and/or reused in various applications (CCU). Examples include blue hydrogen, direct air capture CCS (DACCS) and a range of other fossil-based CCS/CCU value chains.

Blue hydrogen, for example, relies on the extraction of fossil resources from the long carbon cycle and subsequently puts the associated fossil carbon back into the ground. This would then classify as reduction measure and not result in a net carbon removal. However, there are specific engineered value chains where the origin of the captured carbon/CO₂ is either mixed or not directly linked to a specific source. Such value chains could have both mixed reduction-removal impact. This will be the case when the captured carbon is from a mixed biogenic-fossil origin, such as with waste-incineration based CCS, or DACCS which would capture a mixture of fossil-biogenic carbon/CO₂ from the atmosphere.

In this report, when providing examples and a more detailed discussion, we limit ourselves to the 'carbon farming domain' as illustrated in Figure 3 (i.e., nature-based category in the above). However, many of the valorisation and governance issues and challenges described in this report will also apply to the other two main categories.

Figure 3: Overview of climate impact of carbon farming activities

Figure 3 provides an overview of a series of carbon farming activities that each have their own climate performance:

- **Fossil CO₂ reduction:** use of efficient agricultural vehicles, own generation of solar energy, production and application of organic fertilisers and production and delivery of liquid CO₂
- **CH₄ reduction:** manure management, livestock management, and feed measures
- **Soil CO₂/N₂O reduction:** land use management/change, improved fertilizer use/management
- **Natural carbon sinks:** carbon sequestration in soils and above ground biomass, such as the planting of trees (agroforestry), green fallow, perennial grassland, use of organic fertilizers, and paludiculture (e.g., watercress)
- **Humanmade carbon sinks:** cultivation and harvesting of biobased raw materials for use in construction, bio-based chemicals, etc.

1.2 Policy and economic context

International

In 2021, COP26 negotiations addressed carbon removals at different levels. On the one hand, initiatives for the protection of natural sinks were announced. The Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use (UN, 2021) includes 141 countries that committed to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030. However, the 2014 New York Declaration on Forests (UN, 2014) had already announced this target. Indeed, according to IPCC Special Report on Climate Change and Land (IPCC, 2019), reducing global deforestation and promoting forest restoration range among the most effective measures for natural carbon removals.

The Paris Agreement allows for trade of emission reductions, referred to as Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs). As an important prerequisite for integrating ITMOs, including carbon removals into the policy architecture of climate mitigation at COP26 in Glasgow, rules for international carbon markets under Article 6 of the Agreement were completed. The new rules include important requirements and safeguards for engaging in international carbon markets. The agreed rules should help raise ambition, avoid double counting, ensure environmental integrity, and promote sustainable development. However, concerns have been raised that constraints on markets could considerably undermine climate mitigation efforts (see for example (OEKO, 2021).

Article 6.2 requires that any transfer of carbon market units must be reflected in entries in GHG inventories in both trading countries, referred to as "corresponding adjustments". This approach ensures that only the buyer country can use transferred emission reductions, and thus avoids "double counting". Moreover, under Article 6.4, comprehensive rules for a new carbon crediting mechanism were established, similar to the Clean Development Mechanism. It requires that a small proportion of 2% of the transferred units accrues to the atmosphere, referred to as overall mitigation in global emissions (OMGE).

European

The EU climate policy framework comprises of three key pillars:

- the European Emissions Trading Scheme covering mainly energy and industry sectors, (EU, 2022)
- the EU's Effort Sharing Regulation (EU, 2022a) covering the non-ETS sectors such as the built environment, transport, agriculture, and non-ETS industry and waste, and
- the Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation (EU, 2022b).

Aside from that, there are a broad range of EU policy frameworks and initiatives that have a significant climate impact or direct interaction with EU climate policy. For example, the EU's Common Agricultural Policy via the eco-schemes (EU, 2021) also aim to address climate change and stimulate carbon farming activities. At the Member State level, there also is a broad range of policy instruments for non-ETS sectors. Under the RED-II (EU, 2021a), there are renewable fuel blending obligations for the transport sector, as well as subsidy schemes promoting the production of renewable energy.

Within The Netherlands, there are several policy instruments and incentive schemes that (in)directly influence carbon farming activities. These can include investment and innovation subsidies³, as well as exploitation subsidies. In addition, there are various policy instruments aimed at agriculture and forestry that do not have a climate objective but could or will have a (major) impact on emissions in agriculture and forestry, such as buy-out schemes for livestock farmers⁴ and other measures to reduce nitrogen deposition (ammonia emissions). In the mix of incentive schemes shown in Figure 4, we focus on incentive schemes with a climate change mitigation objective that could provide some form of exploitation support for one or more carbon farming activities (see Figure 4).

The five incentive schemes are:

1. SDE++: The scheme to stimulate sustainable energy production and climate transition. The SDE++ scheme (RVO, 2021) originally is a feed-in subsidy scheme that provides a subsidy to produce renewable energy. Energy units (kWh, MJ, and m³) were the key performance metric. However, more recently the SDE++ scheme has been redesigned with the aim to reward the climate performance. As such the schemes' key performance metric will shift more and more towards CO₂-equivalents.
2. HBE: The EU-wide blending obligation for renewable fuels in transport (EU, Biofuels, 2018) also enables the administrative trade of blending of obligations in the form of so-called renewable fuel units (RFUs or HBEs in Dutch). In line with RED-II requirements to participate in this HBE scheme, a renewable fuel must have a minimum CO₂ emission reduction performance.
3. EU ETS: The European Emission Trading System (EU, 2022), is a cap-and-trade scheme that aims to reduce the CO₂ emissions of the energy and industrial sector. For example, the use of bioenergy (e.g., solid biomass, biogas) can result in lower emissions at the installation level.
4. CAP eco-schemes: As part of the 2023-2027 CAP reform (EU, 2021), "at least 25% of the budget for direct payments will be allocated to eco-schemes, providing stronger incentives for climate-and environment-friendly farming practices and approaches (such as organic farming, agro-ecology, carbon farming, etc.) as well as animal welfare improvements". Within The Netherlands a scoring system will be developed to determine the specific premium of a range of eligible "eco-activities".
5. The Dutch National Carbon Market (SNK, 2022) issues carbon certificates for the voluntary carbon market. The SNK scheme includes various nature-based activities aimed at reducing emissions and/or sequestering carbon. It should be noted that SNK is not a policy instrument, but an initiative developed by a group of Dutch market parties. Certificates are only issued when a reduction or removal performance claim is not yet part of prevailing climate policy in the Netherlands (i.e., the measure or action must be additional to existing policies).

³ For example, the Dutch investment subsidy scheme 'Demonstratie Energie en Klimaatinnovatie'; DEI+ ('Demonstration Energy and Climate Innovation') also supports technologies/projects in the area of the circular economy, as well as CCS/CCU (RVO, 2019).

⁴ To reduce the level of NO_x / NH₃ emissions and -deposition from agriculture in The Netherlands, a voluntary scheme (LNV, 2021) with a budget of nearly EUR 1 bln. to buy-out livestock farmers is in effect ('Nationale beëindigingsregeling veehouderijlocaties'; Lbv). On top of that, the newly formed national government coalition (2021-2025) has already expressed ambitions to further reduce the size of the livestock sector, possibly also partially enabled via non-voluntary buy-out or farm relocations (VVD, 2021).

Figure 4: Mix of incentive schemes for carbon farming-activities within The Netherlands

Table 3 provides an overview of the eligible actions and measures of the five incentive schemes. The activity scope includes a range of carbon farming and CCS/CCU type activities. In many cases the described activities have a (potential) overlap, which could lead to overstimulation. For example, SNK includes wetland restoration ('Paying for Peat methodology' - (INTERREG, 2020)), whereas the eco-schemes refer to wet cultivation (or paludiculture). Within the HBE scheme, carbon build-up in soils based on better land management is an eligible action, which is similar to a number of eco-scheme activities including perennial grassland and perennial crop. There could also be overlap in the field of CO₂ capture, storage, reuse, and sequestration (CCS / CCU) between the EU ETS (CCS Directive), HBE and SDE++ scheme.

Table 3: Overview of eligible actions / measures for five Dutch climate incentive schemes

Climate incentive scheme		Project type/category/activity	Source
EU ETS		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biomass / bioenergy as substitute for fossil fuels * - CO₂ capture and storage (via CCS Directive) # 	(EU, 2022) (EU, 2009)
Renewable Energy Units for transport (HBE)		<p>To calculate the emission reduction performance of biofuels the following aspects are included (<i>see RED-II Annex V</i>):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emissions from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o the extraction of cultivation of raw materials * o annualised emissions from carbon stock changes caused by land-use change * o processing o transport and distribution o the fuel in use - Emission savings from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o soil carbon accumulation via improved agricultural management * o CO₂ capture and geological storage # o CO₂ capture and replacement # 	(EU, 2021a)

Climate incentive scheme	Project type/category/activity	Source
SDE++	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable heat * - Solar pv / thermal - Renewable gas from biomass * - CO₂ capture and storage # - CO₂ capture and reuse # 	(RVO, 2021)
Eco-schemes (preliminary list)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rest crop, such as grains, hemp fibre * - Early harvesting of crops, such as beets * - Protein crop, such as beans, alfalfa, clover * - Perennial crop * - Long-term / permanent grassland * - Grassland meadow edge * - Grass/clover * - Herb-rich grassland * - Strip cropping * - Mixed cultivation of 2 or more main crops * - Green cover until spring / permanent green cover * - Incorporating grass sod without the use of herbicides * - No / minimum tillage * - Livestock density per hectare * - Woody landscape elements (hedge, hedge, hedgerow, canal...) * - Ecological ditch management * - Green fallow * - Field / meadow edges * - Organic farming (considered 'Green by Definition') * - Wet cultivation / paludiculture * - Extended livestock grazing * - Small-scale plot, lined with landscape elements * - Resilient crops / reduced use of crop protection products * 	(LNV, 2021)
Dutch voluntary carbon market (SNK)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peat land rewetting / restoration ('Paying for peat') methodology * - Conversion of ammonium nitrogen to liquid nitrate nitrogen fertilizer methodology * - Planting trees outside forest (T.O.F.) methodology * - Climate smart forest management methodology * - Smart tire inflators lower fuel consumption of cars methodology * - Permanent grasslands on mineral soils methodology * - Methane emission reduction by adding a supplement to animal feed methodology * - Carbon sequestration in hemp via application in construction materials methodology # 	(SNK, 2022a)

* Refers to carbon farming or carbon farming related projects and activities

Refers to biomass-based reduction and removal activities, such as carbon capture and storage (CCS) and carbon capture and utilization (CCU)

From a governance perspective it is useful **i)** to assess how the spectrum of incentive schemes looks like, **ii)** how it is developing/changing, **iii)** where overlaps are possible and **iv)** how the instruments can/may complement each other. The latter question of the ‘**complementarity**’ of different incentive schemes is important because carbon farming projects will most likely involve a series of linked or integrated activities that take place in one company, a parcel of land, and/or within one value chain. To determine if there is a real overlap in the incentive schemes depends to a large extent on:

- a) The specific description / definition of the eligible activities,
- b) The specific objective(s) of the policy instrument or incentive scheme, and
- c) The calculation rules used to determine the climate impact (emissions, reductions, and removals).

To assess this, the underlying greenhouse gas accounting rules and principles are discussed in more detail in section 1.3 below.

1.3 Greenhouse gas accounting systems

A robust and uniform European certification regime for carbon removals (and GHG emission reductions) will have to provide clarity on how climate performance is determined and calculated. This requires GHG accounting rules for *monitoring, reporting and verification* (MRV).

Monitoring

Monitoring of LMTs can build on existing monitoring systems that were established to document emissions and removals from land use, land-use change and forestry, as established at national level under the UNFCCC. The IPCC provides guidelines and default factors for monitoring and reporting of GHG emissions and removals by differentiating activity data (often area information) and emission factors (intensity of emission or removal by area unit). However, such systems often lack detailed information to differentiate activities and assess impacts of management changes, required for a robust monitoring and reporting of carbon credits. There are also differences how well monitoring of GHG emissions (CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O) and removals (sinks) are currently already assessed. E.g., forest monitoring is a rather well-established system in most countries, organic soil management requires detailed information on site conditions, soil carbon monitoring is more difficult.

Table 4: Uncertainty estimates of GHG emission factors for AFOLU sector activities

IPCC category	Gas	EF uncertainty estimate (-)	EF uncertainty estimate (+)	Uncertainty introduced into the trend in total national emissions (%)
3Db Indirect emissions from managed soils	N ₂ O	200%	200%	11,8
3B5 Indirect emissions	N ₂ O	100%	100%	3,0
3Da Direct emissions from agricultural soils	N ₂ O	60%	60%	3,2
3A1 Mature dairy cattle	CH ₄	15%	15%	1,2

3B1 Mature dairy cattle	CH ₄	38%	38%	1,9
3B3 Swine	CH ₄	100%	100%	1,9
3B1 Mature dairy cattle	N ₂ O	178%	178%	0,5
3A1 Young cattle	CH ₄	20%	20%	0,4
3B1 Growing cattle	N ₂ O	130%	130%	0,3
3A3 Swine	CH ₄	50%	50%	0,1
3B4 Other livestock	N ₂ O	100%	100%	0,4
3B3 Swine	N ₂ O	100%	100%	0,1
3B1 Growing cattle	CH ₄	20%	20%	0,0
5B Biological treatment of solid waste: composting	N ₂ O	49,4%	49,4%	0,4
3B4 Poultry	CH ₄	100%	100%	0,9
3B1 Other mature cattle	N ₂ O	192%	192%	0,0
5C Open burning of waste	CH ₄	300%	300%	0,0
5C Open burning of waste	N ₂ O	300%	300%	0,0

Source: selection of data taken from (RIVM, 2021)

Bringing down the uncertainty ranges for (project-)specific emission factors for LMTs is one of the main monitoring challenges within the carbon farming domain. Uncertainty ranges for N₂O and CH₄ emission factors are often very high within the land use sectors (see Table 4), but also for CO₂ emissions and sinks there still are significant uncertainty ranges in AFOLU sectors (see Box 1 below).

Box 1: Uncertainty range in CO₂ emissions from land use sectors in The Netherlands

“The uncertainty range in CO₂ emissions from 4A1 (Forest land remaining forest land) is calculated at +10% to -12% and for Land converted to forest land at +26% to -21%.”

“The uncertainty range in the CO₂ emissions for 4B1 (Cropland remaining cropland) is calculated at -60% to +61% and for 4B2 (Land converted to cropland) at -45% to +61%.”

“The uncertainty range for CO₂ emissions in category 4C1 Grassland (non-TOF) remaining grassland (non-TOF) is calculated at -60% to +68% and for 4C2 Land converted to grassland (non-TOF) at -220% to +340%.”

“The uncertainty range in the CO₂ emissions for 4D2 Wetland converted to wetland is calculated at -67% to +76%.”

“The uncertainty range in CO₂ emissions for 4F2 (Land converted to other land) is calculated at -3% to +152%.”

Source: (RIVM, 2021)

The Netherlands National Greenhouse gas Inventory Report (RIVM, 2021) provides uncertainty estimates for both the emissions and removals for the agricultural (NIR, Section 5) and the LULUCF (NIR, Section 6) sector. Out of the top-10 sources contributing most to trend uncertainty in the national GHG emissions, five are linked to LMTs (see Table 5).

Table 5: Uncertainty introduced into the trend in total national emissions

IPCC cat.	Category	Gas	Uncertainty introduced into the trend in total national emissions (%)
3Db	Indirect emissions from managed soils	N ₂ O	10,9
1A4c	Agriculture/forestry/fisheries: all fuels	CH ₄	3,6
4C	Grassland	CO ₂	3,4
3Da	Direct emissions from agricultural soils	N ₂ O	3,0
3B5	Indirect emissions	CH ₄	2,7

Source: selection of data taken from (RIVM, 2021)

GHG emission monitoring in land use sectors is challenging because any claimed carbon removal or emission reduction action is likely to be based on dispersed emission sources and/or on vast plots/areas (i.e., agricultural land and forests). Existing in-situ earth observation measurement techniques (like on-site tree measurements, and soil measurements) cannot easily cover large areas of land without becoming too costly. Also, specific (soil-/ site selection) sampling methods could reduce monitoring costs, but often come at a trade-off with the accuracy and reliability of the results. Novel remote sensing techniques have the potential to a) cover more land/larger plots, and b) reduce monitoring costs. However, such new remote sensing techniques are not yet fully commercially deployed at large scales. In the biomass-based domain, this monitoring challenge, is less extreme, because most existing markets already have experience with biomass certification schemes. Those schemes often ask an actor to monitor the physical material flow (i.e., mass balance) across the entire “chain-of-custody” of value chain. One of the key monitoring challenges in this domain lies with monitoring the subsequent “cycles of usage” and “end-of-life” (circular economy), as it may be challenging to keep tracking biomass (biogenic carbon/CO₂). Further developments in monitoring techniques⁵ will make it possible to reach uniform agreements on this subject within the EU.

Reporting and verification

While the monitoring of GHG emissions, emission reductions and carbon removals is needed to keep track of specific climate impacts, establishing fully uniform reporting and verification at the EU level is more challenging. This is mainly a result of the design of the GHG accounting systems that are linked to national GHG incentive schemes. Throughout different climate incentive schemes, and across different EU member states, we observe significant as well as subtle differences in the specific design of the associated GHG accounting systems.

In the following paragraphs we present an analysis of the most important similarities and differences between several elements of the GHG accounting methods linked to the five Dutch incentive schemes (see Section 1.2 and Figure 4). The following topics/elements are briefly discussed separately:

⁵ See the LANDMARC project for novel tools in development <https://www.landmarc2020.eu/>
Guidance report for potential role of carbon offsetting schemes and Paris Agreement

- Method of determining the **project scope or system boundary** (scope 1, 2, 3 emissions), including the coverage of gases, pools and activities;
- Method of **allocation** of emissions and/or climate performance;
- Use (and drawbacks) of standard **default values** and **minimum performance thresholds**;
- Method of determining / **certification of the sustainability of biomass** and/or land use;
- Rules on **transferring emissions, emission reduction** and/or **carbon sequestration** claims; and
- Minimum required duration (**permanence**) of carbon sequestration.

1.3.1 Scope and system boundary

Table 6 provides an overview of the specific policy goal(s) and basic GHG accounting rules for determining the scope and setting the system boundary for the five individual incentive schemes. Note that all five schemes have an ambition to contribute to climate change mitigation (see Table 6 column ‘policy goal’).

CO₂-equivalents as a common key performance indicator

Traditionally, the SDE and HBE schemes have been primarily aimed at the production or blending of renewable energy. Both incentive schemes mainly use(d) energy (megajoules, kWh, m³) as the primary performance indicator, “unit of payment”. The MRV underlying these schemes are, to a large extent, based on well-developed energy monitoring systems.

Table 6: Policy goal(s), GHG accounting scope and rules per incentive scheme (initial assessment)

	Policy goal(s)	Climate-impact	Scope 1	Scope 2 & 3	
				Domestic	Abroad
EU ETS	-Climate	Emissions	Yes, within installation boundary	No	No, but perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification
		Emission reductions	-	Yes, via avoided fossil CO ₂ and CCS of fossil CO ₂	No, but perhaps indirectly via the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
		Removals	No	No, captured biogenic CO ₂ does not receive additional incentive under EU ETS-CCS regime	No, but perhaps indirectly via the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
HBE	-Climate -Renewable energy	Emissions	Yes	Yes, via use energy during cultivation, harvest, transport, processing, and carbon stock changes associated with the biomass feedstock and perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification	
		Emission reductions	-	Yes, avoided fossil fuel, and via CCS and CCR (carbon capture recycling) of fossil CO ₂	

		Removals	-	Yes, via carbon storage in soils and via CCS and CCR of biogenic CO ₂	
SDE++	-Climate -Renewable energy	Emissions	Yes	Yes, via energy usage	No, but perhaps indirectly via biomass sustainability certification
		Emission reductions	-	Partial, via avoided fossil CO ₂ and avoided methane	No
		Removals	Yes, via CCS as separate eligible activity	No	No
Eco-	-Soil & Air -Biodiversity -Climate -Landscape -Water	Emissions	Yes	No	No
		Emission reductions	Yes (?), on own parcel/land	No	No
		Removals	Yes (?), on own parcel/land	No	No
SNK	-Climate	Emissions	Yes	Yes	No (?)
		Emission reductions	-	Yes	Yes, via specific rule within the SNK Rulebook (SNK, 2021)
		Removals	-	Yes	

Differences in scope and system boundary

Although the ETS is primarily aimed at reducing CO₂ emissions, it predominantly relies on energy monitoring systems (where energy consumption is multiplied by emission factors). It is interesting to note that the emphasis in both SDE++ and HBE schemes is increasingly being placed on GHG reductions and carbon removal. This will ensure that CO₂-equivalents, and not energy units, will gradually become the primary performance indicators. The SNK scheme is also primarily aimed at valuing GHG performance in the form of carbon certificates (per tCO₂-equivalent). The eco-scheme (CAP) differs somewhat from this because it aims to achieve multiple (policy) objectives. In addition to climate (greenhouse gases), these include biodiversity, landscape, water, soil, and air.

GHG accounting systems, such as the Greenhouse Gas Protocol (WRI, 2013) distinguish between three ‘Scopes’. Scope 1 relates to direct GHG emissions “that are owned or controlled by the company”, while scope 2 refers to “GHG emissions from the generation of electricity that is purchased or otherwise brought into the organizational boundary of the company.” Scope 3 accounts for all other indirect emissions that are a “consequence of the activities of the company but occur from sources not owned or controlled by the company.” The notion of an organizational (or system) boundary for GHG accounting purposes is very relevant. This system boundary determines which emissions, reductions and removals are included in the accounting, and which climate impacts are excluded.

We use the scope 1-2-3 approach to tentatively discuss some of the key differences between the system boundary applied for GHG accounting for the five incentive schemes. Within the five incentive schemes, the relevant system boundary can come in different forms. Within the EU ETS, one generally speaks about the “installation boundary”, whereas within the eco-schemes the GHG accounting will be more linked to either the “parcel” or “farm-level”. Within the SDE++, HBE and SNK schemes the “project boundary” is more commonly used.

While all five schemes include some form of GHG accounting where a “system boundary” needs to be determined, the schemes differ in terms of the scope of the associated GHG accounting. Table 6 and

Figure 5 show that the five incentive schemes all include Scope 1 emissions. However, they are not uniform when it comes to including indirect emissions. For Scope 2 and 3, we have made an additional distinction between domestic and foreign Scope 2 and 3 emissions⁶.

EU ETS: The EU ETS uses a limited (scope 1) system boundary, usually the installation boundary (emission allowances are issued at the installation level). Because of this restricted approach (Scope 2 and 3 climate impacts are excluded), indirect Scope 2 and 3 effects are not (or only to a limited extent) included when calculating the net climate effect. Within the ETS system, for example, indirect emissions resulting from the use of (solid) biomass are in principle not included. This also applies to the use of liquid biomass within the EU ETS, but then a number of sustainability criteria (i.e., sustainability certification) under the RED-II Directive must also be fulfilled. Part of this (voluntary) biomass sustainability certification is that a certain minimum climate performance must be achieved over the entire bioenergy chain (i.e., life cycle). In addition, within the ETS system there are also GHG accounting rules for the transfer of (captured) CO₂ outside the installation boundary. However, CO₂ emissions may only be deducted from own emissions in case of long-term geological storage (CCS). Depending on the ETS installation type or business activity specific monitoring and reporting requirements may apply (EU, 2018).

HBE: The HBE-scheme (fuel blending obligation) contains a GHG accounting system that is based on Life Cycle Analysis (LCA). Consequently, this scheme includes more indirect Scope 2 and 3-type climate impacts that belong to the project boundary.⁷ In addition to displacement of fossil fuel-related emissions (Scope 1), the HBE-scheme also accounts for:

- Emissions as a result of the cultivation/extraction of raw materials,
- (In)direct emissions as a result of land use change (iLUC),
- Emissions from the processing, transport, and distribution of raw materials.

The combustion of the biofuel is then seen as CO₂ neutral (except for any non-CO₂ emissions). In contrast to the ETS system, it is not possible to transfer CO₂ emission rights or emission reductions directly to other parties.⁸ However, the HBE system does offer the possibility to account for any further positive climate effects resulting from the project, including:

- The build-up of carbon in the soil (due to improved land management);

⁶ Within scope 2, the emissions resulting from the purchase of energy (electricity, heat, fuels) are often included. Scope 3 includes all other (in)directly chain related emissions. For example, scope 3 could also include emissions as a result of indirect land use change (iLUC) in foreign countries.

⁷ Detailed rules for the calculation of the GHG impact of renewable fuels for transport can be found in RED-II, Annex V/VI (EU, 2018).

⁸ Indirectly a transfer of a climate performance could take place within the HBE-regime. This can occur when there is an administrative transfer of guarantees of origin (GoO) for renewable gas from a biomethane producer to a transport fuel supplier via the public gas grid.

- Emission reduction performance via CO₂ capture, (underground) storage; and
- Emission reduction performance from CO₂ capture and reuse.

To determine the combined Scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions, defaults and standardizations are often used. Examples of this are a correction factor for the 'ILUC-effect' (indirect land use change), a bonus for degraded land and a 'methane bonus'. These correction factors are in line with RED-II. In addition to that a minimum GHG performance threshold for biofuels is applied within the HBE-scheme. The HBE system has its own specific MRV rules and requirements that in The Netherlands are implemented and enforced by the National Emissions authority; (NEa, 2022).

SDE++: The SDE++ scheme predominantly accounts for Scope 1 direct emissions. In an advisory report on the SDE++ scheme to the Dutch government, (PBL, 2021) state that: "*due to practical and analytical limitations [...] secondary effects leading to additional greenhouse gas emissions or reductions are not taken into account.*" However, there are some exceptions, such as: "*the emissions from electricity used (Scope 2 emissions) and the chain effects after or during the production process on Dutch territory (Scope 3 emissions) if this concerns the primary CO₂ reduction impact of the activity.*" Also: "*for mono manure-digestion, the avoided methane emissions from manure management are considered part of the primary process and will be reflected in the ranking*". The GHG accounting rules and the associated GHG performance of a given project are an important metric for ranking the different projects that apply for the SDE++ scheme. For those, Scope 2 and 3 indirect emissions are included in the GHG accounting and in most cases standard or default values are used. For instance, the avoided CH₄ emissions (i.e., the assumed avoided CH₄ emissions are the same as the assumed 'methane bonus' under the HBE-scheme).

Eco-schemes: The new eco-schemes (as part of the CAP reform for 2023-27 - (EU, 2021) are still under development. The scoring system (WER, 2020) and the final selection of eligible eco-activities (LNV, 2021) are still subject to change. In line with this, the specific GHG accounting rules for the eco-scheme in The Netherlands are still under development, but as part of the complex scoring system. This will be based on key performance indicators associated with the five distinct policy goals. It can be expected that the GHG accounting will be mainly (Scope 1) parcel- or farm-level specific (not LCA-based) and will not cover (Scope 2 and 3) climate effects, such as indirect emissions or displacement affects off up- or downstream activities. We expect that the GHG accounting rules will be largely based on the IPCC Guidelines for Greenhouse Gas Inventories (IPCC, 2006) in AFOLU sectors.

SNK: As a voluntary carbon market in The Netherlands, the SNK schemes' GHG accounting is more LCA-based, similar to the HBE-scheme. As such, a larger share of the Scope 2 and 3 climate impacts is included in the GHG accounting. An official opinion of the Dutch Ministry of Economic Affairs on the position of the national voluntary carbon market (SNK) relative to national climate policies (EZ, 2019) it is stated that:

"The Climate Agreement is based on the system for monitoring and reporting greenhouse gas emissions agreed in a UN context."

This implies that emissions, reductions, and removals should be measured where they actually take place (i.e., ‘chimney emissions’). This means that the buyer of SNK carbon certificates cannot claim the associated reduction or removal for its’ own compliance purposes. The reduction/removal performance remains in the sector where a project takes place. Although SNK is a domestic voluntary carbon market, in some cases any emission reductions that take place abroad but are the direct consequence of the project carried out in the Netherlands, can also be certified. In a SNK project that reduces transport fuel consumption through smart tyre pumps (SNK, 2021a), the emission reductions in the value chain that may occur abroad can be accounted. SNK also notes that climate projects carried out in the Netherlands can interact with the EU ETS. While for electricity production and consumption, SNK applies a correction in the GHG accounting (SNK, 2020), it does not (yet) apply a correction factor for other products and commodities that fall under the ETS. For example, the use of hemp in construction materials, could reduce the need for concrete that would otherwise have been produced within an ETS installation.

Generic GHG accounting rules for all kinds of possible indirect, cross-border GHG leakage (or displacement) effects are not specified for all project types. For example, the SNK ‘method document’ for paying for peat (INTERREG, 2020) states, with respect to possible displacement of dairy farming to other (peat) areas ('leakage risk'), that:

"As far as it is known, there are no other peat areas in the Netherlands that are nominated to be 'developed' for (intensive) dairy farming. Since SNK looks at the situation within the Netherlands, it does not look across the border for possible relocation."

We can observe that, as far as SNK is concerned, emissions only from domestic displacement effects are included in the GHG accounting while for some project types, foreign emission reduction claims are included in the GHG accounting. Any foreign “upstream” project emissions, for example emissions from cultivation/felling and transport of imported biomass/biofuels, are not accounted for in this project type (i.e., this is in contrast to the accounting rules of the HBE scheme).

If a carbon farming activity could be eligible within two or more incentive schemes, we need to assess to what extent there is overlap (i.e., overstimulation and/or double counting). One way to determine any overlap is to check if the same activity / action is supported within multiple incentive scheme. For this the overview of eligible activities (see Table 3 in Section 1.2) that could be used provided the listed activities are properly described. Alternatively, one could also determine overlap by assessing overlap (double counting) of the claimed GHG performance. For this we use CO₂-eq. as the key performance indicator and the specific scope of the GHG accounting schemes.

We distinguish between the following five (sub)scope(s):

- Scope 1: Direct effects: emissions related to the company/activity
- Scope 2: Indirect effects: energy-related emissions outside own organisation
 - Sub-scope 2.1: Domestic
 - Sub-scope 2.2: Abroad
- Scope 3: Indirect effects: other indirect chain-related effects outside own organisation
 - Sub-scope 3.1: Domestic
 - Sub-scope 3.2: Abroad

Figure 5: Scope of GHG accounting systems of five incentive schemes (based on limited analysis)

We have split up scope 2 and 3 climate impacts into a domestic and foreign impact, as several GHG accounting schemes have chosen to exclude foreign or target only domestic climate effects. We then qualitatively assessed the extent to which all five sub scopes are covered by each incentive scheme (0 = all GHG impacts of sub scope fully excluded and 5 = all GHG impacts of sub scope fully included; see Table 2 for further explanations).

Figure 5 is a first attempt (based on limited analysis) to graphically illustrate the key differences in the scope of the GHG accounting systems linked to the five incentive schemes. Note: GHG impacts can include emissions, reductions, and removals, but also CO₂, CH₄, N₂O, as well as GHG impacts associated with energy and material usage and components.

From

Figure 5, we can derive that the EU ETS, Eco-schemes and SDE++ have a more limited scope with respect to the GHG accounting, while the HBE and SNK schemes apply a broader scope. In Section 1.5 we discuss what implications this could have for carbon farming activities that would be eligible for two or more incentive schemes (i.e., the **complementarity of climate incentive schemes**).

1.3.2 Allocation of emissions

Some emission reduction or carbon removal projects comprise of a relatively simple value chain, such as planting trees on one parcel, any other land use measures (e.g., permanent pasture, wetland reclamation) or activities aimed at energy conservation at a single location (building). This usually involves a single project activity with a clearly defined system boundary.

The value chain (life cycle) becomes more complex when several project activities and multiple locations are involved. An example of this is when different (bio/fossil) raw materials are brought to a processing facility and are upgraded/converted into different products, such as renewable energy and building materials.

Table 7: Mapping of project categories and main characteristics

Typical....	Energy conservation and energy efficiency	Improved land management	Processing and application of biomass resources	Processing and application of fossil resources
	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Bio-based / circular</i>	<i>Circular</i>
Project type(s)	'Car tire on pressure', efficient energy-installations in buildings/vehicles, aqua thermal energy	Peat soil rewetting, permanent grasslands, climate smart forest management	Hempcrete, harvested wood/wood residue products, organic fertilizers, briquettes, liquid biogenic CO ₂ , low emission animal feed measures in livestock	Recycling of diapers, waste material recycling, refuse derived fuels (RFD)
Project- or system boundary	Building, vehicle, installation	Parcel (land or forest)	Value chain from raw material to end-product	Value chain from raw material to end-product
Project-emissions	Due to (additional) energy consumption	Emissions linked to land management (vehicles, such as tractors, placement of drainage piping, dams, supply of plant material)	Transport, processing, distribution emissions and (possibly also) end-use related emissions	Transport, processing, distribution emissions and (possibly also) end-use related emissions
Emission reduction claims	Avoided fossil CO ₂ -emissions (substitution)	Avoided biogenic CO ₂ as well as CH ₄ /N ₂ O emissions	Avoided fossil CO ₂ -emissions (substitution of end-products and avoided combustion of fossil carbon) Avoided biogenic CO ₂ -emissions	Avoided fossil CO ₂ -emissions (substitution of end-products and avoided combustion of fossil carbon)
Carbon removal claims	N.a.	Carbon storage in biomass (e.g.,	Carbon storage in food, feed, materials, chemicals.	N.a. ⁹

⁹ Carbon removal (or negative emission) is not possible within value chains that only rely on the (re)use of fossil carbon. This is because fossil carbon was initially extracted from the underground (long carbon cycle) and thus comprises an addition to the amount of carbon in the shorter carbon cycle. Any permanent CCS or CCU

Typical....	Energy conservation and energy efficiency	Improved land management	Processing and application of biomass resources	Processing and application of fossil resources
	<i>Energy</i>	<i>Land</i>	<i>Bio-based / circular</i>	<i>Circular</i>
		vegetation/trees) and in soils		

Table 7 provides an overview of 4 main project categories with different basic characteristics and different levels of value chain (life cycle) complexity. Typical project types and associated typical system boundaries are mentioned, as well as typical project emissions, reductions, and removals. Table 7 includes a broad spectrum of energy measures, carbon farming activities and activities in the bio-based and circular economy.

The value chain, and thus the calculation of climate performance, becomes more complex when it involves the processing of various (bio)raw materials (of varying composition and origin) for various applications (e.g., energy, plastics, materials). Such complex (or integrated) life cycles resemble a (bio)refinery process, for which - in addition to determining the system or project boundary - also the allocation of the claims of project emissions, emission reduction and/or carbon sequestration to the specific end products becomes relevant.¹⁰ For example, the GHG emissions related to raw material transport, process and combustion will have to be allocated to the different end products of the chain. The existing individual climate incentive schemes typically apply a default allocation method. This is often based on metrics that are easier and cheaper to measure such as the mass balance method or energy content. Currently, there is no full consistency between the allocation methods applied within the GHG accounting schemes of the five incentive schemes. To illustrate the importance of allocation we consider the example in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** with the following specifications:

- Aggregate project emissions = 130 units;
- Gross aggregate reduction = 300 units (of which 180 bioenergy, 70 liquid CO₂ and 50 biomaterial);
- Gross aggregate removal = 50 units (of which 50 biomaterial);
- Price of net reduction = 75 EUR per unit; and
- Price net removal = 125 EUR per unit.

Figure 6 shows the example of a more integrated project system in which a particular type of (cultivated or residual) biofuel is converted into:

- Renewable energy (e.g., biogas, heat, electricity), (reduction);

application making use of fossil carbon could thus at best become climate neutral, and not achieve (and claim) negative emissions.

¹⁰ Allocation of project emissions to different end-products can for example be done based on energy-content, mass (mass-balance), or economic value of the end-products. While many incentive schemes rely on either mass-balance or energy content-based allocation, within the area of carbon farming and bio-based/circular economy these allocation principles may not always be practical (i.e. could be counterintuitive as the GHG accounting may disturb the hierarchies of best use of land and/or biomass resources; biomass cascading, waste hierarchy).

- Liquid CO₂ (e.g., capture and dissipation of biogenic CO₂) (reduction); and
- Bio-based material in which the residue (e.g., solid residue, combustion ash, pulp, digestate) is given a material/raw material application (e.g., as filling material, organic fertiliser, cement additive, construction and insulation materials, packaging materials) (reduction and removal).

In integrated value chains ('biorefinery') where, for example, the raw material is processed at one location, the project related GHG emissions will have to be allocated to the various end products. This allocation will also determine the net climate effect that can be delivered and claimed per end product. This allocation matters, especially in situations where climate incentive schemes differentiate between reduction and removal claims in terms of the level of support (price per ton of CO₂) they provide. Given that there are various (policy and market) initiatives already calling for differentiation between reduction and removal actions¹¹ we can anticipate that this will result in different tCO₂ support prices. With such differentiation there will be an incentive to try to allocate most project-related emissions to the lower valued climate (reduction or removal) claim to optimize the financial revenue from the claimed climate performance(s).

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- Price of net reduction = 75 EUR per unit; and
- Price net removal = 125 EUR per unit.

Figure 6: Allocation project emissions to final products

¹¹ Some reports and papers are calling for separate policy targets for carbon removal (Meyer-Ohlendorf, 2020), and other scholars are calling for separate accounting systems and markets for reductions and removals (K. Lee, et al, 2021).

Assuming full freedom of choice with respect to the allocation of project emissions over the three final products we can optimize our finance by allocating all project emissions to reduction actions. This maximizes the net removal claim, which has a higher value per unit. For the two most extreme allocation scenarios the financial difference would be EUR 2500. Building on this notion, also the specific GHG accounting scope of the possible incentive schemes is relevant, where in some schemes specific project emissions do not have to be accounted, while in other schemes they must be included. Depending on the specific eligibility conditions of the project activities under the different incentive schemes, the specific GHG accounting rules may also affect which incentive schemes will be preferred by market actors.

1.3.3 Default factors and minimum performance thresholds

Default values

To calculate the net climate impact of a carbon farming activity, default values such as emission factors are often used. Emission factors vary in terms of accuracy and complexity (e.g., see IPCC Tier approach - (IPCC, 2019). For example, as part of the EU RED-II rules for calculating the GHG impact of biofuels multiple default calculation values can be used. These include for example:

- A 'methane bonus' for avoided methane emissions.
- A correction factor for CO₂ emissions due to indirect land-use ('ILUC-factor') change, and
- The use of standard (baseline) emission factors ('fossil comparators').

Standard calculation values are applied in the GHG accounting systems of the SDE++, HBE, SNK and ETS regulations. The use of standard (calculation) values usually makes reporting and verification much easier.

simpler. Due to their generic applicability, default values are often relatively conservative values. This is to avoid, for example, the risk of overestimating the reduction of removal claim or not to underestimate project emissions. Depending on the specific incentive scheme there may be some flexibility with respect to choosing default values or more project-specific values. A “one size fits all” default approach towards GHG accounting may result in misrepresentation of the real climate performance for some projects. For instance, this may be a disadvantage for specific projects falling under incentive schemes that rely mainly on the use of simplified default values. While standardization has advantages in terms of monitoring and reporting there should be sufficient consideration for those projects and actors that are outperforming the default performance not only in terms of the quantification, but also (financial) valorisation of the GHG impact.

Minimum climate performance

Within the HBE system based on RED-II GHG calculation rules, a minimum climate performance requirement is set for renewable transport fuels. This means that the carbon footprint of a new biofuel supply chain as per 01-01-2021 must be at least 65% lower than the fossil comparator (baseline) of 94 gCO₂eq./MJ of fuel. The use of minimum performance thresholds can also make sense from a reporting and verification perspective as it could limit the schemes’ implementation costs. An important limitation of the use of minimum performance thresholds is that projects that outperform this threshold do not receive any additional (financial) benefit or incentive.

Example

To illustrate the potential drawback(s) of default values and minimum performance thresholds we use the example of the immediate/direct anaerobic digestion of animal manure (see Figure 7). In this example we want to claim two climate performances:

- Avoided methane emissions from manure storage; and
- Avoided (fossil) CO₂ emissions from use of the biogas.

To arrive at a net emission reduction, both claims should be corrected for the project-related emissions, for example, stemming from the use of electricity from the grid or diesel use during manure transport. For a profitable operation of the manure digester, the ‘biogas’ or ‘carbon farmer’ has a number of options.

The biogas can be delivered to a nearby dairy plant that falls under the **EU ETS** and can avoid part of the costs for purchasing European emission allowances (EUAs) for the use of the biogas (the current market price - March 2022 - is about EUR 80 per ton CO₂). The supplier of the biogas should then in principle be remunerated for the delivery of the usable energy as well as for the delivered climate performance. A limitation, however, is that under the EU ETS only the avoided fossil CO₂ emissions can be counted. In other words, via the EU ETS, the biogas farmer is not financially rewarded for the avoided methane emissions.

Figure 7: Daily anaerobic digestion of animal manure for the production of biogas

The **SDE++** and **HBE** schemes are more suitable for also claiming the avoided methane emissions. Both systems apply the same default “methane bonus” (45gCO₂/MJ energy from manure equivalent to approximately 22.5 kg CO₂ per ton manure). By doing so, both schemes also reward the avoided methane emissions, and not only the avoided CO₂ emissions. However, the methane bonus is a conservative calculation value. More specific methane reduction values (CH₄ - GWP = 34) were determined in a recent study by Wageningen Livestock Research (K. Groenestein, et al, 2020) for three different manure digester set ups. Depending on the specific digester set up¹² these “real” or more project-specific values are significantly higher relative to the default value for avoided methane emissions (i.e., from 13% up to 67% higher).

For all three digester set ups in the WUR study, the “carbon farmer” delivers a higher climate performance than he can claim via the ETS, SDE++ or HBE schemes. The disadvantage of using a standard value in this example is that the additional climate performance (above minimum performance) is not financially valued. Within the SDE++ scheme this can have an impact on the projects’ success as the climate performance is used as a metric for ranking the different projects that are applying for this subsidy (i.e., where a higher ranking increases the chances of obtaining the subsidy).

This is similar to HBE scheme, where under the current GHG accounting regime any additional performance (i.e., higher than minimum performance) does not result in an additional financial incentive. To illustrate, under RED-II for renewable transport fuels, there must be a minimum emission reduction of 65% compared to the fossil comparator. This fossil reference is currently set at 94

¹² E.g. Stable floor, type of digester, type of manure, temperature of the stable/mixed manure.
Guidance report for potential role of carbon offsetting schemes and Paris Agreement

gCO₂/MJ of fuel. Every biofuel chain that has a CO₂ footprint lower than 32.9 gCO₂/MJ fuel (=94 grams minus 65%); thus, it is in principle eligible for the HBE scheme. In the case of manure digestion, where for example bio-LNG is produced, a standard methane bonus of 45 gCO₂/MJ (= ca. 22.5 kgCO₂ t/manure) is assumed. Any biofuel facility that could claim a methane bonus will most likely easily meet the minimum GHG performance threshold. As a result, any additional (above minimum) performance in terms of climate will not be financially valued within the HBE scheme.

Alternatively, the Dutch voluntary carbon market (**SNK**) in principle is more suitable for customising the GHG accounting methodology. Customisation can be done by developing a project specific GHG accounting and monitoring methodology. This tailor-made methodology can be developed by the initiator and verified/validated by SNK and independent experts. This methodology could be developed in such manner that the project specific climate performance (avoided CH₄ and avoided CO₂) can be claimed.

The disadvantage of a tailor-made or project specific GHG accounting system is that it often entails higher MRV costs relative to schemes like HBE and SDE++ that make more use of default factors. To limit these costs, SNK applies a “rule of thumb” that the MRV costs may not exceed 20% of the expected revenues from the sales of carbon certificates. To limit such costs, SNK will also enable programme of activities approach possible in which projects are bundled and MRV costs can be spread over several parties.

This *real-life example* of a carbon-farming project that has challenges with the full financial valorisation of the claimed climate performance is also included in **Annex I: Real life examples**. The root cause for this is the current complexity of the existing climate governance regime and the fact that several incentives are not properly aligned (i.e., not complementary).

In **Annex I: Real life examples** also another example is included of a biomass-based project (bio-based lactic acid) that also has challenges with financial valorisation of scope 3 emission reductions. In fact, within this example the company is likely to face a ‘CO₂-penalty’ (or financial disincentive) due to a resulting moderate increase in Scope 1 emissions, that fall under the EU ETS.

1.3.4 Biomass sustainability certification

Several incentive schemes (i.e., EU ETS, SDE++ and HBE) in The Netherlands already have or will have additional requirements for the use of sustainable biomass. From 2022 onwards, SDE projects will have to use a verification protocol for determining the sustainability of biomass (RVO, 2022). This is comparable to the (voluntary) certification frameworks for establishing the sustainability of biomass that will also apply within the EU ETS as per 1 January 2023 (NEa, 2021) and to the HBE system (EU, 2018). This requirement and main sustainability criteria are derived from the EU RED-II Directive which

addresses biomass use for energy applications.¹³ Greenhouse gas emissions are one of the sustainability criteria, whereby most often the lifecycle greenhouse gas emissions performance is assessed. While the application of biomass sustainability certification is conditional when using biomass within these schemes, the associated life cycle GHG accounting is not or only partially aligned with the GHG accounting applied within the schemes. While the certification schemes offer the option to perform project specific full life cycle GHG accounting (i.e., scope 1, 2, 3), the incentive schemes apply different scopes (see

Figure 5).

The biomass sustainability certification schemes are, in principle, developed for bioenergy value chains. However, the question is whether these are also suitable for other non-energy biomass value chains, where bio-based raw materials are used in the bio-based or circular economy, and for activities aimed at carbon sequestration in non-energy end products. When expanding the coverage of these certification schemes to the bio-based and circular economy, fundamental questions arise in relation to the scope, system boundary and allocation of emissions as discussed above.

1.3.5 Transfer of emissions, reductions, and removals

The five schemes' GHG accounting systems also apply different rules for the transfer of emissions, reductions, and removals from one activity/entity to another. Part of this can be explained by differences in the way the system boundary (Scope 1, 2, 3) is set and the chosen allocation method. Also, in the case of cross-border value chains, often only domestic effects are considered resulting in an implicit transfer of a certain climate impact.

Apart from the basic accounting rules, there can be other specific rules that determine which activity or sector the emission, the emission reduction or removal claim belongs to. For example, when transferred from one activity/sector to another: Does the raw material or semi-finished product also imply a transfer of the associated emissions, reduction, or removal? Or does the climate impact remain linked to the initial activity in the sector of origin? Also, will the carbon stored within bio-based raw materials be transferred from the forest manager/farmer to the manufacturer, supplier, or end user of bio-based building materials?

While GHG accounting rules at the national level are well developed, the mechanisms through which the climate impacts can be transferred throughout the value chain are more complex. The transfer of climate effects for GHG accounting along the different actors within the value chain may have important implications for any climate performance claims, legal liabilities for non-permanence (or

¹³ Biomass use for non-energy applications falls outside the scope of RED-II.

non-compliance) and financial claims (see Figure 8). This will be especially relevant for cross-sectoral, and cross-border transfers within a more compliance driven governance structure (see Section 1.2).

Figure 8: Transfer of climate claims, liabilities, and funding throughout a value chain

As an example, we can take a carbon farmer who stores biogenic carbon in trees through agroforestry. The carbon farmer then has the choice to **a)** leave the tree standing or **b)** cut down the tree and supply the wood for material applications in the building sector. In scenario **a)**, the farmer can claim the carbon storage in his own farm-level GHG account. In scenario **b)** in the case of felling, the carbon is transferred to and (temporarily) stored in the built environment and will end up either in the GHG account of the supplier of building materials or perhaps the GHG account of the end-user (e.g., homeowner). After the transfer (sales) of a certain climate performance claim, there will also be a need to determine if the liability for non-permanence will or can be transferred.

Figure 9: Transfer of climate claims, liabilities, and funding throughout a biofuel value chain

Within the HBE-scheme the fuel supplier¹⁴ is (see Figure 9) the regulated entity that is responsible for ensuring compliance with the renewable fuel blending obligations. The fuel supplier together with the upstream actors that are part of the biofuel value chain (e.g., raw material producer and biofuel producer) will have to have to negotiate the proper terms and conditions of the contract underlying the collaboration. The raw material supplier would have to create a contract with the biofuel producer, and the fuel producer must negotiate the proper contract terms and conditions with the fuel supplier (see Figure 9). Each contract typically includes basic price and delivery conditions of the (intermediate) product, but perhaps also include agreements on the transfer of the climate (or sustainability claim), as well as liability for non-permanence or non-compliance.

The GHG accounting rules for the HBE-scheme (RED-II Annex V) also allow for additional emission reduction actions claims aside from fossil fuel replacement. These emission reduction claims can be part of the same value chain but are not part of the transport sector. For example, the build-up of soil

¹⁴ Excise duty goods location (Accijnsgoederenplaats).

carbon (soil carbon accumulation) due to improved land management will occur within the agricultural sector, and CO₂ capture and storage (CCS) and/or reuse (CCU) in industrial sectors. While these reductions occur outside the transport sector, they can be accounted for via the HBE scheme. As such, these reduction or removal claims may have implicitly been transferred to the GHG account of the transport sector. The question is what the legal (i.e., ownership, liability) and financial implications are of such cross-sectoral climate claim transfers.

Within the SNK scheme there can be multiple entities that make a joint claim on the reduction or removal claim and split the revenues of the sales of carbon certificates. The sales of carbon certificates will not result in a transfer from a reduction/removal performance to another sector (i.e., any reduction or removal claim will remain in the sector where the performance takes place). The carbon certificate buyer (partly) finances the action, while the liability for non-permanence will primarily rest with the project initiator (see Figure 10). Many voluntary and mandatory carbon markets have implemented procedures for addressing the risk of non-permanence and associated liabilities ([link](#)), such as temporary crediting or withholding credits to hedge for the risk of non-permanence. Relevant discussions for example by (B-C. Murray et al, 2012) on this topic already have a long history.

Figure 10: Transfer of climate claims, liabilities, and funding within a voluntary carbon market project

The EU ETS also has specific provisions for transferring emissions to other sectors or installations. For example, CO₂ emissions captured and stored underground for the long term can be deducted from the ETS installation's own emissions, as they are transferred to another legal entity (see Figure 11). Long-term liability for ensuring the permanence of underground storage are critical issues for enabling this type of transactions, both during the operational phase of CO₂ injection into the underground as well as after decommissioning of geological storage reservoirs. The EU CCS Directive (EU, 2009) addresses non-permanence by requiring storage site operators to surrender “emissions trading allowances for any leaked emissions”.

Figure 11: Transfer of climate claims, liabilities, and funding between an EU ETS installation and geological CO₂ storage service provider

While the both the EU ETS and SNK schemes have implemented provisions to address the risk of non-permanence, the eco-scheme, SDE++ and HBE schemes do not appear to address non-permanence issues. Clear and transparent legal and financial rules regarding the transfer of emissions, reductions and removals between specific activities, companies, sectors, and countries are needed to avoid double counting, overstimulation. If not, legal disputes about ownership of climate claims and liability for non-compliance and non-permanence are likely to arise, especially if these climate claims will have an increasing economic value.

1.3.6 Risk of non-permanence

The EU ETS Directive, in conjunction with the CCS Directive, refers to long-term storage of CO₂ in underground geological formations. The monitoring of storage sites must also take into account any leakage of CO₂. The regulations clearly signal an intention to capture CO₂ and store it permanently for a long period of time. Although no exact storage time horizon is given, it is expected to be at least 100 years.

The HBE-scheme several options to account for carbon removal in soils, underground storage, and reuse. The relevant EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED-II) states that carbon accumulation in soils may only be counted if there is sufficiently reliable evidence that the amount of soil carbon has increased or that an increase can reasonably be expected during the period in which the biofuels (intended for biofuel production) are grown. The RED-II directive (HBE-scheme) thus seems to use a different, much shorter, time horizon for the permanence of carbon sequestration (i.e., biofuel crop rotations can sometimes be shorter than one year). With regards to the re-use of captured biogenic CO₂, a one-to-one displacement (reduction) of fossil CO₂ can be claimed within the HBE system. Potential removal of the same biogenic CO₂/carbon in for example long-lived biomaterials is not (yet) accounted. For any CO₂ capture and storage, the RED-II (and HBE system) explicitly refers to the CCS directive which is linked to the EU ETS system.

To date, no generic rules for non-permanence have been established within the SNK scheme. SNK applies a more specific approach, where for each method document (project type) fair non-permanence provisions are put in place. A key issue of ongoing debate is what fair and relevant time horizons are when requiring different projects to ensure the permanence of carbon removal. Knowing that there are quite a few approved SNK method documents focusing on carbon-farming or nature-based solutions (SNK, 2022a)¹⁵ one can anticipate a relative high risk of non-permanence. Currently, as a rule of thumb the SNK scheme applies a minimum guaranteed storage duration of 10 years or

¹⁵ Such as planting trees outside of forests, permanent pasture and wetland reclamation, and projects that use bio-based materials (hempcrete).

more. To date, SNK has not accepted any applications with a claimed permanence less than 10 years (e.g., such as within the method document under development for crates made from hemp).

Given the nature of the removal activity (nature-based) and the characteristics of the liable organisation (a farm or private entity), it may not be fair to request for removal permanence guarantees that last much longer than 10 years. However, there are certain SNK project types (e.g., climate smart forest management or planting trees outside forests) that are managed by reliable organisations with different characteristics (for example nature conservation agencies or public bodies) that should be able to plan and ensure permanence over longer time horizons.

The issue of non-permanence will also play a role for many of the eligible eco-activities of the eco-scheme. CAP payments will be made conditional upon the implementation for eco-activities that deliver specific climate and other eco-system services. Whether any reclaim of the CAP eco-scheme payments is foreseen on the basis of non-permanence of reduction/removal performances (i.e., reversal of the intended climate effect) is not clear.

The risk of non-permanence is particularly prevalent in the carbon farming domain and can be problematic for the carbon farmer's business model and in case the incentive scheme(s) will reclaim part of the funding based on non-permanence. While - depending on the sector, activity or incentive scheme - there are different strategies to manage the non-permanence risk (e.g., collective non-permanence fund, issuance of temporary carbon certificates, or non-permanence insurance products similar to crop insurance), but these will come at a cost for the carbon farmer. These long-term 'insurance' costs will have an immediate impact on the business case of the carbon farmer.

1.4 A changing framework of incentives

In sections 1.2 and 1.3, the GHG accounting systems of five existing climate incentive schemes are discussed in more detail. However, this 'framework of incentives' is of temporary nature. Most of the mentioned incentive schemes are subject to change.

SDE++: The SDE++ scheme (and its predecessor, the MEP scheme) exists since 2003. Over the years, this scheme has been updated and modified several times. New eligibility conditions and new project categories can be added each year (annual cycle of revision). New project categories can be added based on new insights, and the associated GHG accounting system can also be adjusted from time to time.

HBE: The HBE-schemes' renewable energy units (HBEs) offer fuel suppliers the possibility to meet their renewable fuel blending obligations, either physically or administratively by trading HBE units. The current energy unit-based scheme will probably be replaced in the near future by a system based on tradable greenhouse gas units (BKEs). The Netherlands has already implemented the basic legal framework for the **BKE** scheme. However, the date of entry into force is still uncertain. In a review

(Raad van State, 2020) of the BKE scheme, the Netherlands Emissions Authority (NEa)¹⁶, among others, is questioning the added value of the scheme relative to the HBE system. One of the main critiques is that the BKE-scheme may not be sufficiently fraud-resistant, and it may also be difficult to enforce. The risks related to proper monitoring of GHG emissions throughout the supply chain are explicitly mentioned in this respect; particularly because (i.e., in the case of biofuels) most of the emissions take place abroad.

Eco-schemes: The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) intends to create a so-called eco-scheme. In The Netherlands, the level of the CAP premium (bronze, silver, gold) will depend on the contribution of an eligible eco-activity (see Table 3) to the various CAP goals. Currently, a scoring system for eco-activities is being developed (WER, 2020) and an associated simulation tool tested (Rijksoverheid, 2022) within The Netherlands. This scoring system will assign points to an eco-activity based on key performance indicators (KPIs), including net greenhouse gas emissions. This scoring system will become part of the CAP National Strategic Plan (Rijksoverheid, 2021) for the period 2023-2027.

EU ETS: The European Emission Trading System (ETS) is operational since 2005. It is a so-called cap-and-trade system (EU, 2022) in which a decreasing amount of CO₂ emission allowances (cap) are available for the installations in the regulated sectors. The allocation of these allowances can be free (depending on the nature of the economic activity¹⁷), but they are increasingly auctioned by governments. In addition, ETS installations can also trade emission allowances with each other, to ensure compliance (i.e., be able to surrender sufficient emission allowances to cover their own emissions). This system has also been amended several times throughout the years, for example through the inclusion of a market stability reserve ([link](#)) and changes with respect to the allocation of emission allowances. In addition, in 2021 the European Commission (EC, 2021) proposed to extend the ETS to other sectors such as (road) transport and the built environment. Such a sectoral expansion of the ETS scheme would then also assign an economic value to emissions (reductions and removals) that now could (partially) fall under the HBE or SDE regime.

SNK: Within the Dutch voluntary carbon market, only reductions or removals can be certified on the basis of measures that they are additional to current policies (SNK, 2020a). In practice, the additionality of a project type is not always easy to determine and may require a project (type) specific approach. For example, a landowner receives a (non-SNK) nature conservation subsidy for meadow bird protection. This subsidy is conditional upon a certain number of breeding birds counted in the subsidised plots. The subsidy schemes terms and conditions also provide a recommended groundwater level that would be favourable for the birds' habitat. The landowner receiving this nature conservation subsidy can only get SNK carbon certificates for these parcels if the groundwater level is raised above the recommended groundwater level. This assessment of additionality, however, is likely to change through time as the specific terms and conditions of the different incentive schemes change. Within

¹⁶ The Netherlands Emissions Authority (NEa) is the competent authority for the execution and enforcement of the EU ETS and HBE-scheme.

¹⁷ See EU ETS 'Carbon leakage' list, here: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/eu-action/eu-emissions-trading-system-eu-ets/free-allocation/carbon-leakage_en#ecl-inpage-1251

the voluntary carbon markets, such as SNK a periodic re-assessment of the additionality of specific projects and project types will be needed. This typically is done when a SNK project requests for an extension or renewal of the project certification period. Alternatively, to ensure additionality an SNK project - that is also eligible for another incentive scheme (e.g., the SDE++) - could also explicitly declare to refrain from claiming the subsidy in order to obtain carbon certificates via the SNK.

Policy additionality

Additionality is particularly complex when a project consists of a value chain with subsequent emissions, reductions, and removals. While for certain parts of the value chain, no instrument is in place yet (and therefore the activity is additional), other activities in the same value chain may be subject to / or eligible for other incentive schemes or policies. For this activity, the additionality may need to be (re-)determined.

In principle, carbon certificates and subsidies can be combined. SNK assesses the policy additionality as well as the policy complementarity for each project type and documents this in the respective methodology document or via the general rule book (SNK, 2022a). The methodology document is updated annually on this point, or when necessary, based on policy developments.

Other incentive schemes would also benefit from a periodic “policy additionality” and “policy complementarity” check, especially after the respective scheme has been modified. This could minimize the risk of overstimulation and/or double counting.

In addition to the five incentive schemes discussed in this report, there are several other potentially relevant schemes which interact with each other. These include incentive schemes in the domain of the bio-based/circular economy, as well as investment subsidies such as the Dutch Demonstration of Energy and Climate Innovation scheme (DEI+) (RVO, 2019). This report, therefore, is not an exhaustive overview of all relevant policies and incentive schemes but is intended to provide insight into the problems of coexisting or parallel incentives that interact in practice. These interactions may lead to results in practice that strongly deviate from the theoretically expected results of the instruments.

Keeping track of cross-border climate impacts

Similar to the critique on the Dutch BKE scheme, the SNK scheme also faces the challenge of effective controlling and monitoring the direct and indirect climate effects of all links in the cross-border value chain. This is similar in relation to the EU ETS scheme, where the aim is to minimize carbon leakage (i.e., cross-border displacement effects) because of the more stringent European climate objectives. To (partially) address this issue, the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism; CBAM (EC, 2021) has been proposed. CBAM must ensure that the climate impact of imported products is better reflected in the (import) price.

To better map out cross-border direct and indirect climate effects, better MRV systems for a broad range of i) carbon farming, ii) bio-based economy and iii) circular economy activities and value chains will be required. The sustainability certification schemes for (imported) biomass for energy applications offer good starting points for performing a full life cycle analysis. Most of these (voluntary) certification schemes such as [ISCC](#), and [Better Biomass](#) also assume the monitoring of GHG emissions

throughout the full life cycle “chain of custody”, and often allocate emissions on the basis of mass balance accounting. However, these certification schemes have mainly focussed on renewable energy systems and less on (non-energy) bio-based/circular economy value chains for the (re)use of biogenic and fossil raw materials. For such integrated systems that use different inputs and produce different energy and non-energy outputs, it will be a challenge to correctly allocate emissions as well as the reduction and removal claims to the various end products (see The existing individual climate incentive schemes typically apply a default allocation method. This is often based on metrics that are easier and cheaper to measure such as the mass balance method or energy content. Currently, there is no full consistency between the allocation methods applied within the GHG accounting schemes of the five incentive schemes. To illustrate the importance of allocation we consider the example in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.** with the following specifications:

- Aggregate project emissions = 130 units;
- Gross aggregate reduction = 300 units (of which 180 bioenergy, 70 liquid CO₂ and 50 biomaterial);
- Gross aggregate removal = 50 units (of which 50 biomaterial);
- Price of net reduction = 75 EUR per unit; and
- Price net removal = 125 EUR per unit.

Figure 6).

1.5 Complementarity of climate incentives

For any SNK scheme project that integrates several economic activities within the same value chain or on the same parcel, or where the different climate claims are valorised via a mix of different incentive schemes, it will be more difficult for SNK to determine the additionality of the action (SNK, 2020a). This additionality issue is similar also for other (climate) schemes where policy additionality is often also a basic conditionality. In such circumstances it will no longer be sufficient to assess whether or not an activity can be called additional; rather it will be more meaningful to determine under what circumstances and conditions the incentive schemes can be combined (i.e., are complementary to each other). To assess the complementarity of incentive schemes, it needs to be fully clear which incentive scheme supports which activity and funds what part of the climate performance. This is not only to avoid over-subsidisation or double counting of the same climate actions and climate claims, but also to provide clarity to the market which combinations of incentive schemes under what conditions are allowed.

Given the expected increasing complexity of integrated and cross-border value chains within the bio-based economy, circular economy, and carbon farming domain. Clear rules are needed for determining policy complementarity (i.e., which schemes can be combined?).

To clearly assess the complementarity of incentive schemes, it may be necessary to split up certain individual components or activities from the value chain and/or to include them in a separate project or system boundary in the scheme(s) GHG accounting system. The isolated activity with its associated

can then more easily be funded via a specific scheme. However, this would require that all incentive schemes apply only Scope 1 GHG accounting and ignore any up- or downstream Scope 2 and 3 impacts (see Section 1.3.1).

It is to be expected that within the carbon farming domain (see Figure 3) different climate claims can be made under a mixture of incentive schemes. A carbon farmer producing and using organic fertilizers could choose to valorise the avoided fossil CO₂ emissions due to the substitution of chemical fertiliser via the SNK scheme similar to e.g. the approved SNK Greenswitch method by (M. van Oers, 2020), while the soil carbon accumulation could be valorised via the CAP eco-schemes or HBE scheme under improved land management. Another example is the application of biochar (soil carbon accumulation) and forest planting (carbon accumulation in vegetation). Both climate actions could be implemented at the same time on the same parcel. Here, for example, the soil carbon accumulation could be valorised via the European Biochar Certificate ([link](#)), while accumulation of carbon in above-ground vegetation is valorised via the SNK scheme (similar to e.g. 'Planting forest and planting outside forest' method (M. Boosten et al, 2021). In addition to this, the climate impact from the bioenergy (derived from the production biochar or the combustion of harvested/thinning wood) could then possibly be valorised via the SDE++ scheme.

These simplified examples indicate that there is a need for clear rules on the complementarity of climate incentives. The example of the manure digester from Figure 7 shows that there are different routes to monetise the two climate performances (avoided CH₄ and avoided CO₂) in the carbon farming domain.¹⁸

Table 8: Possible combinations of incentive schemes for valorisation of avoided CH₄ and CO₂ emissions via manure digestion

Combination	Avoided CH ₄	Avoided CO ₂
1	SNK - 51 – 75 kgCO ₂ /t manure	EU ETS
2	SDE - 22,5 kgCO ₂ /t manure (default saving) SNK - 29-53 kgCO ₂ /t manure (additional saving)	SDE++
3	HBE - 22,5 kgCO ₂ /t manure (default saving) SNK - 29-53 kgCO ₂ /t manure (additional saving)	HBE
4	SDE - 22,5 kgCO ₂ /t manure (default saving) SNK	SDE++ - adjusted for EUA price EU ETS

¹⁸ One could make a similar analysis of climate activities/projects within the bio-based and circular economy domain where there are a broad range of activities that capture and/or reuse (biogenic) carbon (CCS, CCU).

	- 29-53 kgCO ₂ /t manure (additional saving)	- EUA price (per t CO ₂)
5	SNK - 51 – 75 kgCO ₂ /t manure (full project-specific saving)	SNK

The example raises questions about the **complementarity** of the SNK, SDE++, HBE and ETS schemes and their associated GHG accounting systems. Under what conditions can you accumulate / combine different incentive schemes and when is it considered double counting or over-stimulation? From a theoretical perspective the following five combinations of incentive schemes are conceivable (see Table 8). Below we briefly discuss five possible combinations.

Combination 1: Currently there is no specific rule within the Dutch voluntary carbon market (SNK, 2022a) that rejects this combination with the ETS. However, there is a rule on the interaction with the EU ETS regarding the calculation of CO₂ emission reductions for renewable electricity (SNK, 2020). To date, no methodology documents have been submitted to the SNK that foresee such a combination. The fact that both reduction effects are the result of a single project activity makes it harder to classify the avoided CH₄ as additional. On the other hand, the EU ETS does not valorise the avoided CH₄. At the time of writing, it is not fully clear if SNK would classify such an emission reduction claim as 'additional to existing policy'.

Combinations 2 & 3: In the past, SNK has received some draft proposals for emission reduction claims from manure digestion (where SNK and SDE++ scheme could potentially be combined). While there have been internal discussions at SNK on the issue of policy additionality, no final ruling or decision was taken for this combination. Since recently, the GHG accounting system of the SDE++ system also includes a standard/default value for avoided methane emissions.¹⁹ The key governance question is, if the difference - between the actual avoided and the default avoided CH₄ emissions – can still be claimed via the SNK scheme. In fact, this difference concerns an above-legal-minimum climate performance and could, in principle, be considered additional. Such a nuanced dialogue with regards to the complementarity of SNK-scheme with the SDE/HBE-schemes has not taken place within the SNK to date.

Combination 4: This combination is similar to combination 2 with the addition of the EU ETS. The rules of the SDE scheme indicate that the Dutch government has the right to adjust the SDE++ subsidy amount in case of 'any additional income related to the sales of CO₂ emission rights' (PBL, 2021a). The correction will be based on an unweighted average market price of EUAs on the European Energy Exchange (EEX). For the time being, this correction seems to apply only to revenues related to the sales of emission allowances within the EU ETS. Application of correction amounts for revenues related to voluntary carbon certificates (via the SNK) seems to be excluded (for the time being).

Combination 5: Although strictly speaking this is not a combination of two different schemes, the voluntary carbon market (SNK) does in principle offer the possibility of fully valorising both climate

¹⁹ The same applies to the HBE scheme, where the same standard value (methane bonus) for avoided methane is applied.

effects (i.e., based on project-specific calculation values) via the SNK system. To this end, the initiator must explicitly state in his/her SNK project plan that during the project period he/she will not claim funding for the activity via other incentive schemes.

The five possible combinations of schemes outlined in Table 8 only capture a limited set of the possible activities and climate claims from the carbon farming domain (see Figure 3 and Table 3). We expect to see similar incentive scheme interactions within the rest of the carbon farming domain, but also within the biomass-based and circular economy domain (see Figure 2) where activities are focussing on emissions, reductions, and removals.

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Annex I: Real life examples

This Annex includes two examples of nature-based, biomass-based project types with a certain climate impact (reduction and/or removal) that are not able to fully (financially) valorise their climate performance(s) under the current policy regime.

The two examples are:

1. Anaerobic digestion (AD) of animal manure
2. Cross-border value chain of next generation lactic acid

Both examples provide real life examples of the limitations of the Scope and coverage of the GHG accounting systems related to individual climate incentive schemes.

Both real life examples were identified and discussed in-depth with several market stakeholders throughout the research process. The AD example was discussed in-depth with several market stakeholders from The Netherlands with experts in the network from the Dutch Centre of Manure Valorization ([NCM](#)). The lactic acid example has been discussed in detail with several experts from the sustainability team of [Corbion N.V.](#)

Based upon the analysis in this report, we expect to be able to identify many more examples of reduction and/or removal projects that will face significant challenges to valorise all their GHG impacts along their specific value chain. To properly map these examples, an intensive dialogue with market stakeholders, as well as research and policy makers is needed.

Anaerobic digestion of animal manure

Summary table

Main category		Main climate impact(s)	Name of activity
Nature-based	X	Reduction	Anaerobic digestion of animal manure
Biomass-based			
Engineered			
		Reduction claim(s)	Removal claim(s)
Country/region (context)		The Netherlands	-
Relevant policy/incentive scheme mix		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Emissions trading scheme (ETS) - Feed-in tariff scheme, rewarding climate performance (SDE++) - Renewable fuel blending obligation (HBE) - Dutch voluntary carbon market (SNK) 	-
Main valorisation issue(s)		Inability to valorise substantial parts of the avoided methane emissions via a single incentive scheme, and unclarity about combinations of schemes are allowed to valorise both climate impacts.	-
Key potential co-benefits		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lower ammonia/NH₃ emissions (air quality) - Improved sanitary / health conditions for livestock - Indirect human health benefits 	-
Potential risks/trade-offs		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting manure digestion may create lock-in for policy makers who have the ambition to reduce the size of the Dutch livestock sector. - Local social acceptance for (mainly industrial scale) manure digesters is uncertain due to few bad experiences in the past. - Business case for manure digestion for the carbon farmer is marginal and risky. 	-
(non-)permanence		N.A.	-
Monitoring challenges		Adequate low-cost methane emission/reduction monitoring from manure management can be costly. Currently causing most schemes to rely on (very) conservative default/standardized emission saving factors.	

Climate impact/claim within the context of the full value chain (life cycle)

The anaerobic digestion of animal manure and production and supply of biogas has two distinguishable climate impacts. The produced biogas will substitute fossil energy (natural gas or fuels), which will result in 'avoided fossil CO₂' emissions. The biogas can be used directly (for heating), or further processed into biomethane (grid injection) or bio-CNG/LNG for use in transport. In addition to that, the anaerobic processing of animal manure will result in lower methane ('avoided CH₄') emissions from manure management (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: Valorisation options of GHG impacts of anaerobic digestion

Valorisation of the climate impact

To claim (and valorise) both climate impacts (reductions) the ‘carbon farmer’ will have to look which incentive schemes are available that would support both the investment and exploitation of the activity of running a biogas plant. There are four possible incentive schemes that could potentially valorise both climate impacts via:

- The EU Emissions Trading Scheme (ETS)
- Non-ETS subsidy scheme sustainable energy production and climate transition (SDE++)
- Non-ETS renewable fuel blending obligation for transport (HBE)
- Domestic voluntary carbon market (SNK).

ETS: The carbon farmer could decide to supply its biogas directly to an EU ETS company via a dedicated biogas pipeline. The EU ETS company would then obtain the energy and would be able to claim avoided fossil CO₂ emissions as natural gas (or another fossil fuel) is substituted (56,4 kgCO₂/GJ). This CO₂ emission reduction represents a monetary value under the EU ETS (equivalent to the EUA price). However, the avoided methane emissions cannot be valorised via the EU ETS, as this emission reduction takes place outside the ETS installation boundary. So, via this route the carbon farmer can only receive a partial financial reward for both climate impact.

SDE++: The SDE++ scheme was originally designed to support the production of renewable energy, including the production of biogas via a feed-in subsidy in non-ETS sectors. More recently, the subsidy scheme was redesigned to focus more on reducing CO₂ emissions. The production of biogas is an eligible activity for the SDE++ scheme. The subsidy will be awarded to projects that have the highest

climate effect per EUR of subsidy (ranking). However, while the SDE++ greenhouse gas calculation method fully includes the CO₂ savings from the substitution of fossil energy, it only partially accounts the CH₄ emission reduction. In the accounting system a standard / default CH₄ emission reduction factor ('methane bonus') of 22,5 kg CO₂eq./t manure is used, while the real CH₄ reduction performance could be considerably higher at 62 kg CO₂eq./t manure depending on the specific set up of the manure digester project.

HBE: The Dutch system for blending of renewable fuels for the transport sector, relies on booking and claiming of so-called renewable energy units (HBE's). The biogas produced by the carbon farmer can enter the transport sector either physically or administratively. Direct on-site bio-LNG production (liquefaction of biogas) would enable direct supply to the transport sector by a regulated fuel supplier. Alternatively, the biogas can be upgraded to biomethane and injected into the gas grid. The biomethane can be administratively supplied to a fuel supplier with the help of guarantees of origin. Once the biogas-derived renewable fuel has entered the transport sector a HBE unit can be booked, claimed, and traded for compliance. As such and HBE unit represents a monetary value. However, before the biogas can be supplied to the transport sector the fuel supply chain needs to meet a certain minimum greenhouse gas emission reduction threshold (i.e. -65% emissions) relative to the fossil comparator (94 kg CO₂/GJ). The GHG accounting rules for HBEs²⁰ are more elaborate than the SDE++ GHG accounting system but apply the same default / standardized value for the CH₄ emission savings ('methane bonus'). Within the HBE system any 'overperformance' relative to the minimum required threshold is not valorised (i.e. doing better relative to minimum GHG compliance is not financially rewarded).

SNK: The Dutch voluntary carbon market (SNK) provides an incentive for projects/activities that aim to reduce/remove greenhouse gas emissions that is additional to existing policy targets and instruments. SNK can be seen as a 'last resort' incentive scheme for valorising GHG impacts in case existing government policies do not provide an adequate incentive. In principle, claims on reduction of CH₄ emissions, as well as avoided fossil energy related CO₂ emissions can be eligible in the voluntary carbon market. The specific GHG saving would depend on the project-specific baseline or reference scenario. Current SNK rules ('rulebook') indicate that in case a project explicitly indicates not to make use of other existing government support/incentive schemes (like ETS, SDE++ and HBE), the activity can be eligible under SNK. The benefit of this option would be that a carbon farmer would potentially be able to claim the full/real GHG savings (avoided CH₄ and CO₂) because of its actions. The associated carbon certificates could then be sold on the voluntary market. The downside would be that the carbon farmer would have to design and implement a robust GHG monitoring plan to substantiate its reduction claims. The costs associated with a tailor-made monitoring protocol, proper reporting, and verification (MRV) and certification can be substantial. These costs are typically higher than the MRV costs of the

²⁰ See RED II, Annex V / VI.

ETS, SDE++ and HBE schemes, which rely more on standardized approaches. The revenues of the sales of carbon certificates on the voluntary market should thus be sufficient to a) cover for these additional costs, and b) ensure a sufficiently stable financial revenue stream for the carbon farmer.

Potential co-benefits, risks, trade-offs, (non-) permanence issues

Anaerobic digestion of animal manure could also contribute to lowering NH₃ emissions from manure management and possibly also N₂O emissions. However, this depends on the specific design, set up and management of the post-treatment of the digestate, as there may also be certain trade-offs.²¹ Improved sanitary conditions for livestock can contribute to improved livestock health conditions, and lower usage of veterinary services and medicines. Improved manure management may also reduce the loads or occurrence of antimicrobial resistant bacteria²² (pathogens) in the environment, which could have significant human health benefits.

²¹ See: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29415114/>

²² See: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-6382/11/3/391/pdf>

Cross-border value chain of next generation lactic acid

Summary table

Main category	Main climate impact(s)	Name of activity
Nature-based		
Biomass-based	X Reduction	next generation technology for lactic acid
Engineered		
	Reduction claim(s)	Removal claim(s)
Country/region (context)	The Netherlands	
Relevant policy/incentive scheme mix	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Emissions trading scheme (ETS) - Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism - EU Sustainable Carbon Cycles - Ecodesign - Feed-in tariff scheme, rewarding climate performance (SDE++) - Foreign voluntary carbon markets 	
Main valorisation issue(s)	<p>The Scope 3 emission reductions achieved by using the new technology are not rewarded.</p> <p>The new technology results in a significant reduction in Scope 3 emissions outside Europe but a (much smaller) increased use of energy (to enable an internal recycle). This increases Scope 1 emissions within Europe. Due to the Eu price of Scope 1 emissions in the ETS, using the new technology increases the ETS costs for this lower-emission value chain.</p>	
Key potential co-benefits	Reduced use of other chemicals	
Potential risks/trade-offs	First of a kind plant (risk/opportunity)	
(non-)permanence	Depending on application (e.g. food <i>versus</i> recycled packaging or building and construction application)	
Monitoring challenges	Corbion monitors its cradle to gate emissions for each manufacturing site. Option A in the proposed carbon tracking approach report would be suitable: Report-Carbon-Tracking-System.pdf (topsectorenergie.nl)	

Climate impact/claim within the context of the full value chain (life cycle)

Many products are made from polymers. Most polymers are made out of fossil material, but new bio-based polymers from renewable materials are being developed. Many of them have a lower CO₂ footprint and can contribute to the circular economy. Next generation (bio-based) lactic acid can result in significant CO₂ emission reductions relative to traditional fossil-based polymers.

Bio-based polymers are made from renewable materials, such as sugar cane. While growing, these crops can absorb significant amounts of CO₂ from the atmosphere. Depending on the application, this CO₂ is captured for a longer or shorter period. At the end of the life cycle(s) the carbon is emitted back into the atmosphere as CO₂.

The new technology for lactic acid production eliminates the use of lime as a raw material. This reduces the cradle to gate carbon footprint of lactic acid by about 20%. Next to its existing plant in Thailand, Corbion is currently building a 2nd plant in Thailand that will use this technology.

The existing plant in Thailand uses conventional technology that results in an already favourable footprint of -224 kg CO₂ per ton of lactic acid as depicted in Figure 13.

Figure 13: CO₂ footprint of existing lactic acid value chain

The new plant will use the new next generation technology – with a much lower cradle to gate footprint (-465 kg CO₂ per ton of lactic acid), but higher direct emissions at the lactic acid plant (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: CO₂ footprint of next generation lactic acid value chain

Corbion's next plant in Europe will also use this new technology and we expect additional improvements based on experience with the technology in Thailand.

Valorisation of the climate impact

For the valorisation of the climate impact of the next generation lactic acid value chain, the EU ETS, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) and (voluntary) carbon markets are key relevant incentive schemes.

Given that the EU ETS, predominantly accounts for Scope 1 emissions the higher Scope 1 emissions in the next generation value chain will act as a financial penalty (disincentive) to lower Scope 3 emissions. Within the given example, (voluntary) carbon markets in the non-EU country (i.e. Thailand) could provide an incentive to financially offset the EU ETS Scope 1 financial penalty. But this depends on the specific scope, rules, and conditions for (voluntary) carbon markets within the source country. An alternative strategy could be that CBAM provides a positive incentive to offset the ETS Scope 1 penalty. CBAM could provide a positive financial incentive for importing low GHG commodities, such as bio-based lactic acid. The current CBAM seems to be designed to avoid ‘carbon leakage’ ([link](#)), which should financial disincentivize the import of high GHG emission commodities and products. A carbon border tax would act as financial penalty to the import of high emission commodities and products. The lactic acid example shows that – under CBAM - there may also be a need to positively incentive the imports of lower emission bio-based commodities from outside the EU to offset the ETS Scope 1 financial penalty. Currently, under CBAM organic chemicals, like lactic acid are still excluded from its scope (see (EC, 2021) on p.19):

“In particular, organic chemicals are not included in the scope of this Regulation due to technical limitations that do not allow to clearly define the embedded emissions of imported goods. For these goods the applicable benchmark under the EU ETS is a basic parameter, which does not allow for an unambiguous allocation of emissions embedded in individual imported goods. A more targeted allocation to organic chemicals will require more data and analysis.”

Table 9: Functional substitutes/replacements of bio-based (poly)lactic acid

Product benchmark	How do LA/PLA compete?	Benchmark value 2021 - EUA/t product for 2021-25 (link)
Lime	Very CO ₂ intensive input and cannot be recycled. Corbion’s next generation LA process recycles all chemicals, so lime is no longer required.	0,725
Adipic acid	Both adipic acid and LA can be used to produce plastics	2,120
Styrene	Input for polystyrene, which competes with PLA	0,401
Mineral wool	Competes with PLA for thermal isolation purposes	0,536

Within the EU ETS bio-based lactic acid installations currently fall under the heat fallback benchmark. This is problematic since producing heat is not the primary goal of lactic acid (and polylactic acid). While the derived bio-based products are not (chemically) identical they do act as a functional substitute/replacement for fossil equivalents, such as lime, adipic acid, styrene, and mineral wool (see Table 9).